

**From Minor Omissions to Full Bans: The Mechanisms and Perceived Impacts of
Censorship in Translated Children's Literature in Iran**

MA Thesis

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Summary

This study investigates the phenomenon of censorship in translated children’s literature in Iran, focusing on its mechanisms and Iranian children’s perception of its implications for them and their rights, addressing a significant gap in the existing literature by exploring how censorship is implemented through translation and its effects on the perception of the Iranian child reader. The theoretical framework employed for this investigation integrates multiple theories to provide a comprehensive understanding of censorship in translated children’s literature, with key concepts including cultural translation and cultural hegemony, drawing on the works of Sarah Maitland and Antonio Gramsci to examine how censorship in translation takes place and how the practice could be manipulated to align with specific ideological goals. For the second part of the study, reader-response theory, particularly the perspectives of Louise Rosenblatt and Wolfgang Iser, is combined with developmental psychology to explore how Iranian children perceive, interpret, and interact with censored texts, the analysis of which is further enriched by a discussion on children’s rights, particularly the right to access diverse and uncensored information.

The research methodology combines textual analysis of three widely recognized titles—*Harry Potter and the Sorcerer’s Stone*, *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, and *The Da Vinci Code*—with interviews of sixteen Iranian adolescents. The textual analysis reveals various censorship mechanisms, such as omissions and alterations that are driven by religious regulations. Moreover, the interview results indicate a nuanced understanding among participants of the censorship they have encountered, with varied reactions ranging from frustration to resignation and acceptance. Finally, the thesis concludes by advocating for the protection of

children's rights to have free access to uncensored texts and emphasizing the need for further research in this area.

خلاصه

این مطالعه به بررسی پدیده‌ی سانسور در ترجمه‌ی ادبیات کودک در ایران می‌پردازد و تمرکز آن بر مکانیزم‌های سانسور و درک نوجوانان ایرانی از پیامدهای آن برای خودشان و حقوقشان است. این پژوهش با بررسی چگونگی اعمال سانسور از طریق ترجمه و اثرات آن بر درک نوجوانان ایرانی، شکاف قابل توجهی را در تحقیقات موجود پوشش می‌دهد. چارچوب نظری این تحقیق با ادغام نظریه‌های مختلف به درک جامع‌تری از سانسور در ادبیات کودک ترجمه‌شده می‌پردازد. مفاهیم کلیدی از جمله ترجمه‌ی فرهنگی و هژمونی فرهنگی با بهره‌گیری از آثار سارا میتلند و آنتونیو گرمشی تعریف شده‌اند و چگونگی وقوع سانسور در ترجمه و نحوه‌ی استفاده از این عمل برای پیش بردن اهداف ایدئولوژیک خاص را بررسی می‌کند.

در بخش دوم مطالعه نظریه پاسخ‌گویی خواننده، به‌ویژه دیدگاه‌های لوییز روزنبلات و ولفگانگ ایسر، با روانشناسی رشد ترکیب شده تا بررسی کند که نوجوانان ایرانی چگونه متون سانسور شده را درک، تفسیر و با آن تعامل می‌کنند. تحلیل این بخش با بحث در مورد حقوق کودکان، به‌ویژه حق دسترسی آزاد به اطلاعات متنوع و بدون سانسور، غنی‌تر می‌شود. روش تحقیق این مطالعه، تحلیل متنی سه عنوان شناخته‌شده، یعنی هری پاتر و سنگ جادو، ماجراهای شرلوک هولمز، و کد داوینچی است که با مصاحبه با شانزده نوجوان ایرانی ترکیب می‌شود. تحلیل متنی، مکانیزم‌های مختلف سانسور، از جمله حذفیات و تغییرات تحت تأثیر قوانین اسلامی را آشکار می‌سازد. نتایج مصاحبه‌ها نشان‌دهنده‌ی درک دقیق شرکت‌کنندگان از سانسور‌هایی است که با آن مواجه شده‌اند، واکنش‌هایی از ناامیدی گرفته تا حس پذیرش و تسلیم در برابر رژیم. در نهایت، این پایان‌نامه با تأکید بر نیاز به تحقیقات بیشتر در این زمینه و حمایت از حقوق کودکان برای دسترسی آزاد به متون بدون سانسور پایان می‌یابد.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

“Censorship and auditing are against freedom of expression... essentially, the auditing system is a system against human rights,” said Kambiz Norouzi (2024, own translation), lawyer and journalist, in a panel for the Iranian Association of Writers for Children and Youth during which the impact of new censorship regulations on Iranian children’s literature was discussed. According to the report later published on the panel, the censorship that is taking place in Iran makes authors, translators, and readers feel unsafe in their work and reading practices, respectively (Yahyapour, 2024). On the same topic, Shahram Eghbalzadeh, translator and literary critic, tells the Association in an interview that “the post-Revolution policies have failed. Right after the Revolution, we used to have books published in 10,000s and 15,000s, but it has now been reduced to as small a number as 500” (as cited in Yahyapour, 2015, p.1, own translation). He goes on to state that “according to surveys on people’s lack of interest in reading, many of the readers have lost their trust in books published in Iran, and this is due to the pre-publishing censorship.”

While this disinterest in reading resulting from censorship has been studied in Iranian adult readers, censorship also happens in Iranian children’s literature at different stages of publishing and distribution, the implications of which have not been studied so far. From the publishing editor to the librarian choosing the book, adults hold authority over what books children get to read (Sigler, 1999). Whether by the political authorities or by the educators, the act of censorship can be viewed as limiting the child’s free access to reading material and thus violating children’s rights.

It has been previously argued that after the Islamic Revolution in 1979, cultural suppression has been a key element of the post-Revolution government’s ruling style (Moore, 2016). More

specifically, in 1994, by the Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution's vote, an organization was formed for the first time in charge of pre-publishing screening of children's literature, which remains active as a branch of the Iranian Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance. While censorship of media in general is common knowledge in Iran (Article 19, 2006), in the case of children's literature, this censorship is defined as a form of auditing or screening with the aim of children's moral protection against harmful material (Yaari, 2015). Despite some efforts by translators to circumvent censorship using various tactics (Haddadian-Moghaddam, 2014), free access to texts for Iranian children is still an issue.

Following Bishop's metaphor of mirrors, windows, and sliding glass doors (Bishop, 1990), books can be a place for children who seek to find their own lived experiences reflected in the mirror of literature they consume, in addition to being a window for young people to learn about others' lives and develop a better understanding of the world they live in. Censorship of children's books, therefore, either before or after publishing, denies children both this representation of self and understanding of others.

In a context where censorship of children's books is legally taking place, young people in majority groups do not have the chance to learn about different groups of people and their experiences in life, while young people from Iranian minorities do not see themselves represented in the media. On the issue of cultural erasure via censorship, Kaambiz Norouzi (1998) stated that "censorship is an act based on which everyone is pushed to the culture desired by the government. It prevents other cultures and beliefs from flourishing." In other words, limiting children's access to diverse material is a way for the government to assimilate different minorities into one culture, thereby homogenizing a culturally diverse community.

Another aspect of censorship of children's literature manifests itself through children's interest in themes that are censored out of texts for their specific age groups but may be available in adult literature, resulting in children's diminishing interest in available texts, which could, in turn, cause them to resort to adult literature that is not always easily comprehensible for younger age groups and can contain material that is not suited to their specific age. In the case of Iran, lack of access to diverse children's books has led to children trying to educate themselves through adult content (Hejazi, 2011), the effects of which have yet to be studied.

In such an oppressive environment, there has not been much, if any, research done on the process of pre-publishing censorship of children's literature through translation. When it comes to censorship of children's literature, most of the existing research, as far as the literature review for this study has obtained, is centred around pedagogical censorship in the US and other Western countries (Curwood et al., 2009; Davila, 2022; Hunt, 1997; West, 1996). On the other hand, research on censorship in Iran looks at the bigger picture and inspects censorship of arts and literature in general (Article 19, 2006; Karimi-Hakkak, 1990; Hejazi, 2011). Therefore, there exists a research gap on censorship of children's literature in the Islamic Republic of Iran, whether political, pedagogical, economical, or an amalgamation of them.

By addressing this gap, this study aims to raise more awareness on the issue of censorship in translated children's literature in Iran, which has not yet been studied despite its prevalence in the country, and consequently, investigate its impacts on Iranian children. The results of such research could illuminate the implications of the current state of censorship in Iran for children, helping educators and guardians make more informed decisions regarding this matter in the future, whether by attempting to change regulations in a more democratic Iran in the future or by simply educating children on how to approach censored texts more effectively. This investigation is

guided by the following research questions: How does censorship via translation take place in children's literature within Iran? Additionally, how is this practice and its impacts on children and their rights perceived by the children themselves? These questions seek to uncover the mechanisms of censorship and the subjective experiences of young readers in relation to censored texts.

To answer these questions, the initial phase of the research focuses on examining how censorship of children's literature in Iran through translation happens by closely analysing three titles translated and published in Iran for adolescent readers, particularly emphasizing themes censored due to conflicts with religious regulations. Subsequently, the second section aims to shed light on the impacts of the system of censorship present inside the country on children's perception of their rights to have the freedom to access texts and their opinions on censorship in general. This will involve individual interviews with a group of sixteen teenagers, aged between 15 and 17 years old, who will be given the aforementioned translated titles to read and later discuss in the interview. The focus of these interviews will be to ask their opinions on the censorship present within these books, in addition to gathering their broader views on the practice of censorship in Iranian children's literature at large and its impact on their rights.

The structure of the following chapters is designed to first provide the necessary background information in the form of a comprehensive literature review, covering several key topics, including censorship, children's literature, translation, and their presence in an Iranian context, upon which a theoretical framework unique to this study is constructed that will be utilized in the following chapters to dissect the censored translations, and effectively interpret the interview results. The next chapter will delve into an elaborate explanation of the methodologies employed for this research to provide a clear research design, the rationale behind the choice of texts, the selection process for the interviewees, and the data collection and analysis methods. The

subsequent chapter will focus specifically on the textual analysis of the three selected texts. The aim is to conduct an in-depth analysis, highlighting the instances and nature of censorship related to religious issues.

The sixth chapter will present the results of the interviews, which will include a thorough exploration and interpretation of the perspectives and lived experiences of the interviewed teenagers in Iran. This section will offer insights into the children's attitudes towards censorship and its impact on their reading choices and habits. Finally, the last chapter will attempt to summarize all concluding thoughts from the previous chapters. This conclusion will aim to address the original research objectives set out previously in the paper. The chapter will discuss the implications of these findings for theory and practice. Additionally, it will identify potential avenues for further research on the area, given the significance of the research in the broader context of children's literature and censorship in Iran.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The phenomenon of censorship has long been the subject of intense scholarly debate, raising critical questions about freedom of expression, cultural control, and its impact on readers (Karolidis et al., 2005; Post, 1998; Butler, 1997). While such debates are prevalent across different global contexts, they take on unique colours in regions where political and religious ideologies heavily influence the mechanisms of censorship. This can be particularly evident in the specific landscape of translated children's literature in Iran, where the existing research proves lacking.

This literature review follows a thematic order and aims to first explore the multifaceted dimensions of censorship at large and then its dynamics in the field of children's literature, moving on to how these dynamics unfold in Iran, especially after the 1979 Islamic Revolution. The review will then narrow down to examine how censorship is manifested through the translation of children's literature in particular, finishing with the current literature on the impacts of this practice on children and their perception of their rights.

2.1. Censorship and Literature

The first found use of the word 'censor' refers to Roman magistrates who took the census and supervised public morals (*The Columbia Encyclopedia* 2008). The English word 'censor' comes from the Latin *censere*, meaning to appraise, value, judge, consider or assess. In its modern usage, 'censor' referred to people who held the job of ensuring written material did not include anything immoral or offensive to the State. (*OED*) In practice, censorship has been described as "the knot that binds power and knowledge" (Jansen, 1988, p.4), a bind that remains at the centre

of the relationship between censorship and literature, further proving that censorship and literature have always had an intertwined existence in society (Moore, 2016). In Moore's entry for *Oxford Research Encyclopedias*, she explains that:

Censorship defines the literary by outlawing that which it is not allowed to be; literature shapes censorship by exploring and contesting its limits. Institutionally, and insofar as literature has a public and reading is a collective act, censorship has been literature's determining other. And insofar as censorship in its modern incarnation is cotemporaneous with print culture and dependent for its character on the media technologies and forms of literacy grown by that age, literature has been its most persistent and prominent antagonist. (Moore, 2016, p. 2)

Building on the historical and conceptual foundations of censorship, it becomes evident that the dynamic interplay between censorship and literature is not simply a matter of restricting content but a complex negotiation of cultural values and power. This relationship demonstrates the dual nature of censorship as both a limiter and a definer of the scope of literary expression.

As literature continues to push the boundaries of what is considered acceptable, censorship responds by recalibrating the limits of literature's operation. This cyclical interaction suggests that while censorship attempts to confine and define the literary landscape, literature itself acts as a force of resistance, constantly challenging and redefining those boundaries. In other words, censorship does not simply suppress content, but also inadvertently contributes to the evolution of literary expression, creating an environment in which literature and narratives continue to evolve to reflect and resist these limits.

2.2. History of Censorship in the Islamic Republic of Iran

In Iran, censorship of children's literature also existed before the 1997 Islamic Revolution, but with different goals in mind. During the Constitutional era (1905-1911), also regarded as the period of Enlightenment in Iran, the intellectual reformists defined specific criteria for children's literature based on their pedagogical views that they imported from their years in the Western countries. Educational authorities of the time believed the existing Persian tales to be outdated and aimed at infusing the pedagogical material of the schools with European literature (Ghaeni, 2017). Mohammad Hossein Foroughi, one of the authorities responsible for the educational system of Iran during this period, believed that,

these folktale books are not proper for our children. They spoil our children's minds. They include insults and absurd words. The classic Iranian literature is too complicated for them, but we cannot substitute the love stories which are retold by illiterate people. (Mohammadi et al., 2017, p. 256)

Furthermore, Mirza Taghi Kashani, another Iranian educator and writer, criticized folktales and called stories about beasts, goblins and giants "full of nonsense to decay and deceive the children" (Mohammadi et al., 2017, p. 257).

Looking at censorship in the past four decades of Iran's history after the Islamic Revolution in 1979, one can see that cultural suppression has been a key feature of the post-Revolution government (Moore, 2016). In 1994, the Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution voted for the formation of an organization to control the content of children's books. The board, whose members

are chosen by the Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance, are to vote for or against the books that are to be published. Board members are authors of children's literature as well as Islamic experts. Former board member, Mohammad Reza Sarshar, said in an interview that "those who were against censorship at that time were liberal and believed in anarchism. They wanted to promote their ideology through their cultural products" (Motamednejad, 1998, p. 41).

Regardless of the initial crackdown on the publishing houses after the Islamic Revolution and the establishment of specific organizations to control the content of books, the publishing industry in Iran did have the chance to flourish during the first two decades after the Islamic Revolution. Initially, this was due to the government's preoccupation with other post-Revolution issues like the Iran-Iraq war (1980-1988), but the leading role was played by President Khatami's reformist government (1997-2005) taking a more permissive route toward publishing, which resulted in a rapid rise in the number of publications from 1997 to 2005 (Marchant, 2014). However, starting with Ahmadinejad's presidency in 2005, the publishing industry saw a tightening of regulations, with publishing houses and bookshops being closed under the guise of technical issues (Mollanazar, 2010). The harassment of writers and publishers escalated up to 2013, which resulted in the number of published books plummeting during Ahmadinejad's eight years of presidency (2005-2013), a period of explicit cultural authoritarianism (Marchant, 2014).

An issue that arises on the sidelines of the field of censorship is that in the context of the Islamic Republic of Iran, where governmental policies and strategies are founded upon Islamic principles, it is still impossible to understand the clear rules for the actual practice of literary censorship, which "remains vague and in constant flux" (Grigor, 2014, p. 142). In other words, writers do not have clear guidelines for what is acceptable for children and what is not. This can be both confusing and frustrating for writers when, for instance, one particular book keeps getting

rejected after multiple audits and editing while similar topics have been published before under the same rules and regulations.

In the last decade, the censorship of books in Iran has gained momentum, leading to children's literature writers turning to diaspora publishers to have their books published outside of the Islamic Republic of Iran in order to prevent potential censorship; this is usually done through independent Persian literary organizations in the West that help writers publish and distribute their books without going through the rigorous auditing by the Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance first (Marchant, 2014).

In a way, censorship of children's literature under the rule of the Islamic Republic of Iran has given even more incentive to writers for young people to work against the grain and fight the lack of adequate material for children caused by the oppressive regime. With the help of both online and diasporic publishing, the new generation of Iranian writers of books for young people produce free, accessible material for Persian-speaking children; however, they are not accessible inside the country due to restrictive cultural policies (Marchant, 2014).

2.3. Censorship in Translated Children's Literature in Iran

The translation of children's literature is a dynamic field where culture, language, and societal values meet, something that is further highlighted in the context of Iran, due to it being an Islamic state strictly adhering to Islamic laws. The regulatory censorship by the Iranian Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance has shaped a literary landscape where translated children's literature must navigate through layers of censorship dictated by the authorities in order to reach its audience. In other words, the Ministry acts as a gatekeeper of texts circulating within Iran,

ensuring that all literature, including translations targeted at children, adheres to Islamic values and, consequently, the government's ideological stance (Ahmadi, 2022).

Translators in Iran employ various strategies to cope with this practice of censorship. In a survey done on 47 translators working in Iran,

Eleven argued that they prefer not to adopt a work that is likely to receive substantial censorship. Two translators self-censor their translations... One respondent says that she continues translating and keeps them for a suitable time for publication... She is probably hoping for a political change in Iran where there are no restrictions, censorship, or control by the government. One respondent says that he translates according to the political situation. Two translators use adaptation, an intra-linguistic process of accommodation to new culture, to the requirements of official censorship to escape censorship (Haddadian-Moghaddam, 2014, p. 132).

These efforts reveal a community grappling with constraints that limit the scope of accessible literature in addition to the integrity of the translation process. These adaptations and acts of self-censorship, while pragmatic, point to broader implications of such stringent controls: a diluted cultural exchange and an inhibited cultural and intellectual freedom, which in the present context can impede the development of critical thinking and open-mindedness in adolescent readers. The following subsection further elaborates on the impacts of censorship on the Iranian child reader.

2.4. Impacts of Censorship on the Iranian Child Reader

Books are sometimes windows, offering views of the worlds that may be real or imagined, familiar or strange. These windows are also sliding glass doors... When lighting conditions are just right, however, a window can also be a mirror. Literature transforms human experience and reflects in back to us... Reading, then, becomes a means of self-affirmation, and readers often seek their mirrors in books. (Bishop, 1990, p. ix)

In other words, books are not always simply a window to look through and see other lived experiences. It is important that children seek to find their own image in the mirror of the literature and media they consume. In addition, children's books are a sliding glass door for all children to understand the experience of other groups better. For instance, books containing LGBT themes do not serve the sole purpose of a mirror for LGBT children or children coming from LGBT parents. They also help all the other young people learn about those children and develop a better understanding. Censorship of children's books, either before or after publishing, robs children of this experience. In a country where censorship of children's books is rampant, young people do not have the chance to learn about different groups of people and their experiences in life. In this context, the publication and distribution of children's books "[have] generated silences and rendered some cultural experiences invisible." (Botelho, 2021, p. 124)

Regarding this issue of erasure of identities and experiences, it should be noted that Iran is a country composed of various ethnical groups –Kurdish, Azari, Balouch, and Arab, to name a few– with children who do not get to see themselves in the published books inside the country. Furthermore, as explained in the previous paragraph, children in the majority groups do not have

the opportunity to learn about minorities while growing up. In such a context, limiting children's access to diverse material could be a way for the government to assimilate different minorities into one culture, therefore erasing their identity.

2.5. Summary

As explained in this review, censorship of children's literature happens at different levels and for different reasons. Regarding children's literature, most of the existing research is centred around pedagogical censorship in the United States and other Western countries. These studies shed light on the controversies and reasonings surrounding post-publishing censorship by parents and educators, as well as covering the topic of self-censorship by authors and publishing editors. Previous literature on the censorship of children's literature pays little attention to the political side of the censorship of books for young people in countries with oppressive governments.

On the other hand, research looking into censorship in the Middle East, and more specifically, in Iran looks at the bigger picture and inspects censorship of arts and literature in general. Therefore, there is a noticeable gap in the current body of research on censorship of children's literature in Iran. Furthermore, there have been no previous studies on the practice of censorship in Iranian children's literature that takes place through translation. As illustrated in this review, the importance of access to global and diverse children's literature warrants more attention to censorship of children's books under the rule of the current Islamic Republic government.

In conclusion, by looking at the currently available studies on censorship of children's literature, censorship in Iran, and the effects of censorship on children, this review covers the history of the topic at hand over the last four decades and analyzes the current trends in the practice

of censorship and publishing under governments exercising censorship. Furthermore, the effects of such trends on children, especially Iranian children have been looked into. However, it is worth taking into account that there is a gap in studies regarding the exact up-to-date mechanisms of censorship of Iranian children's literature and how they affect each generation of children growing up in Iran.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework

In a society like Iran, where the number of translated titles is on a constant rise compared to books by local authors (SNN, 2022), translation plays a crucial role in people's reading habits. The act of translation inherently denotes alteration and change in its process of transferring information, a characteristic that may be employed in several ways, censorship being one of them, to create certain desired outputs and feed into certain power dynamics. Furthermore, as previously discussed in the introduction chapter, censorship of literary works in Iran is a recurrent and regularly discussed topic. However, in the context of children's literature, while blatant and acknowledged, this phenomenon has not received much scholarly attention. To address this gap, this paper aims to answer two main questions, the first being: How does censorship of children's literature through translation take place in Iran? And the second one being: How is this practice of censorship and its impacts on children and their rights perceived by the children themselves?

3.1. Maitland's *Cultural Translation*

In order to answer these questions, it is essential to become familiarized with the key concepts of this research, namely translation, censorship, and children's rights. To define the first key concept, translation, Sarah Maitland's (2017) definition of cultural translation has been incorporated. According to Maitland, cultural transition takes form through attendance to a transcendent political or ethical concern for others' wellbeing and to the awareness of contingency and context. Against this background, cultural translation becomes an inherently political or ethical matter. Cultural translation is a phenomenon connected to how a subject interacts with the other, a

process during which there is the risk of mere reproduction of what one already knows while ignoring specific details due to the unfamiliarity with and lack of access to the other's experiences.

This concept emerged in response to the limitations of traditional translation theories that focus primarily on linguistic equivalence and fidelity, such as in models proposed by Nida and Taber (2003) that emphasize formal and dynamic equivalence and often overlook socio-cultural and political contexts that influence the translation process; therefore, Maitland's idea of cultural translation, which views translation as an act of cultural mediation rather than mere linguistic transfer, provides the required framework for understanding translation as a dynamic and interpretative process embedded in cultural and ethical contexts.

In her work *What is Cultural Translation* (2017), Maitland posits five main points. The first one is that meaning is always produced during communication, and is not merely transferred. Secondly, in this process of production, the involved persons create themselves as subjects. The third point states that these created subjects actively try to find the best mode of communication. In other words, the involved subjects work out what they know as best and then tailor the information to fit the other's understanding. Additionally, as the fourth point, Maitland explains that this tailored knowledge is always filtered through the subject's point of view and judgments. Finally, this process is dynamic and ongoing, bound up with one's constant act of interpretation.

While Maitland's theory of cultural translation is influential, it is not the only framework available for analyzing the translation process, with some other significant theories being Gideon Toury's (1995) Descriptive Translation Studies (DTS) which puts focus on describing what translations do in their cultural contexts, rather than prescribing what they do, and examines the norms and conventions that shape translation in various cultural contexts, and Hans Vermeer's (1989) Skopos theory, which posits that the purpose of a translation should determine its strategies,

emphasizing the functional aspects of translation. However, despite the merits of these theories, Maitland's concept of cultural translation is particularly well-suited for this research for a number of reasons, the first being its focus on ethics and politics and foregrounding the ethical and political dimensions of translation, which are crucial for understanding the practice of censorship in the context of Iran.

Secondly, Maitland focuses on the dynamic and ongoing nature of translation, which resonates with the complex realities of translating children's literature in a strictly controlled cultural context like Iran. In addition, the theory's relevance to cultural hegemony, the next theory chosen for this research, makes it particularly useful; in other words, by viewing translation as an act of cultural mediation, Maitland's theory complements Gramsci's concept of cultural hegemony, providing a cohesive framework for analyzing how state ideologies might be propagated through children's literature, and resulting in a theoretical synergy that can enhance the analytical depth of the study.

3.2. Gramsci's *Cultural Hegemony*

Taking a close look at how state ideologies can be promoted in children's literature and their underlying power dynamics is further facilitated by the use of the theory of cultural hegemony. Developed by Antonio Gramsci in 1971 in line with his Marxist beliefs, cultural hegemony is defined as the ruling class's domination over a culturally diverse society through cultural means, a process that happens via cultural institutions like language and literature, among others (Bullock et al., 1999). Gramsci's theory emerged in the context of early 20th-century Italy

in response to the limitations he saw in classical Marxist theory with its primary focus being on economic determinism, arguing that the ruling class also exerts control through ideological means.

The theory of cultural hegemony stands among other significant theories related to the states' exertion of power, such as the classical Marxist theory of ideology, which focuses on the role of economic structures in shaping society but fails to fully account for the subtle and pervasive nature of ideological control through cultural institutions (Hoare et al., 1971). Another theory in this field is Althusser's (2001) Ideological State Apparatuses (ISAs), which include education institutions, media, and culture, as functioning to reproduce the ideology of the ruling class but lacks Gramsci's nuanced emphasis on the active role of subordinate groups in consenting to and perpetuating their dominance.

Finally, Michel Foucault's (1977) theory of discourse and power offers another perspective on how control is exercised in society, arguing that power is pervasive, operating through discourses that shape knowledge and truth, with his focus being more on the micro-mechanisms of power and how they operate via various practices, rather than on the ruling state's control over cultural products. Therefore, Gramsci's theory of cultural hegemony was chosen due to its comprehensive approach to understanding how ideological control is maintained through cultural means, which is particularly relevant for analyzing the role of censorship in children's literature, highlighting the ways in which censorship is not merely about the omission of sensitive material, but can play a role in shaping the cultural and ideological landscape to reinforce the existing power structures.

3.3. Censorship, Where Cultural Hegemony Meets Cultural Translation

While according to the Oxford Companion to the English Language, translation is “the communication of the meaning of a source-language text by means of an equivalent target-language text” (Bhatia, 1992, p. 1051), the process of translating texts entails more than the mere conversion of text from one language to another; translation also involves a complex negotiation with the target culture’s norms, values, and in this case, censorship regulations. Maitland’s definition of cultural translation is helpful here as it lends the necessary tools to study the nuances of the translation norms in Iran, which may act as a conduit for alterations that reflect the dominant ideologies (Bassnett et al., 1998).

This interplay between cultural translation and cultural hegemony highlights how the practice of censorship, which can be defined as a socio-political process involving the regulation, suppression, or control of information, ideas, and artistic expressions deemed objectionable or harmful by authorities, institutions, or societal norms (Post, 1998; Jansen, 1988), serves to maintain social order, protect cultural values, and uphold political power and structures, which is essential to understanding the mechanisms of censorship through translation in the landscape of Iranian children’s literature and answering the first question posed in this research.

3.4. Rosenblatt’s and Iser’s *Reader-Response Theory*

To fully address the second research question—how this act of censorship affects children’s perception of their right to have free access to media, it is beneficial to first engage with reader-response criticism. The choice of reader-response theory as part of the theoretical framework for this research has been deliberate, as it provides a framework to explore how children interpret

censored texts, recognizing them as active participants in meaning-making rather than passive recipients of texts (Bennett, 1995), which stands in contrast to more traditional theories like formalism or structuralism.

While different categorizations exist within this school of thought, for the purpose of this paper's theoretical framework, the focus is on the transactional reader-response theory, originally proposed by Louise Rosenblatt and later expanded upon by Wolfgang Iser. This perspective asserts that meaning arises from a dynamic interaction between the text and the reader's individual interpretation, influenced by personal experiences and context (Iser, 1978), which aligns with the study's objective of understanding how Iranian child readers interpret censored texts and the broader implications for their perceptions of their rights. This theory, therefore, can help the research explore how censorship can shape not just children's understanding of a text but also their worldview and self-conception.

3.5. Erikson's *Developmental Psychology* and Identity Formation

Borrowing from the vast area of developmental psychology, this paper seeks to reach a better understanding of how children are affected by the practice of censorship and what the implications are for their rights. According to developmental psychology, and more specifically Erikson's ideas on stages of development, adolescence, which encompasses the age group studied here, is a period for identity formation characterized by the psychological conflict of identity vs. role confusion (Erikson, 1968). In other words, during adolescence, individuals explore various roles, beliefs, and ideas to develop a cohesive sense of self. Developmental psychology puts particular emphasis on the importance of developing a sense of identity during this period as it has

a lifelong effect on the person and is related to a child's curiosity and active engagement and failure to do so could result in role confusion and a weak sense of self (McLeod, 2024).

In addition, this theory underscores the importance of diverse stimuli for holistic growth, which is hindered by restrictive translation practices since the literature that adolescents are exposed to plays a significant role in this developmental process, providing them with a means for exploring different perspectives, values, and experiences. However, by limiting children's exposure to a wide range of ideas and perspectives, censorship may undermine the child reader's capacity for comprehension and lead to an obstacle in children's growth. Thus, according to developmental psychology, the act of censorship not only affects immediate access to information but also has deeper implications for the foundational development of adolescents' sense of identity and autonomy.

It is important to note that Erikson's idea of stages of development is not the only significant theory in this field; other significant theories include, but are not limited to, *social identity theory* (SIT), developed by Henri Tajfel and John Turner (1979), which posits that individuals derive a significant part of their identity from the social groups they belong to. In the context of this study, SIT can be relevant in understanding how Iranian adolescents perceive their identity in relation to the dominant social and cultural groups. Another relevant theory would be Urie Bronfenbrenner's (1977) *theory of ecological systems*, examining how different environmental systems interact and impact one's development, ranging from immediate microsystems, such as family and school, to broader macrosystems, such as cultural values. This theory can be helpful in understanding the layered impact of censorship on identity formation through an analysis of how various environmental factors, including attitudes towards censorship and other national policies, collectively influence children's sense of self. While these theories

offer rich perspectives on identity formation, developmental psychology, particularly Erikson's stages of development, is chosen for this research due to its focus on the intrinsic stages of identity development, providing a structured framework to investigate how censorship influences the critical phase of identity formation.

3.6. Reader-Response Theory and Developmental Psychology: A Synthesis and Its Implications for Children's Rights

The censorship of children's literature via translation has significant implications for children's rights, particularly their right to access diverse information outside of the cultural norms of their context. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) emphasizes children's right to freedom of expression and access to information, signalling the importance of exposing children to a range of ideas and viewpoints, which is undermined by censorship and restricting the flow of information and, consequently, limiting the diversity of narratives available to young readers.

Integrating reader-response theory with developmental psychology creates the framework required to understand the implications of this restriction. In the context of censorship, reader-response theory highlights how children might engage with texts differently when they are aware of the potential of censorship, which could, in turn, lead to a sense of distrust and diminished reading experience. This can then result in stifling the development of critical thinking and interpretative skills, acting as an obstacle to adolescents' exposure to diverse ideas that would allow them to compare different perspectives and reflect on their personal values—an obstacle that, according to developmental psychology, can be detrimental to children's self of identity.

Moreover, the moral and ethical dimensions of children's rights regarding literature are also significant, as children's rights are not just about legal entitlements but also considerations regarding the quality of life that future generations experience, making it crucial to provide children with access to a broad range of literature as a way of respecting their intellectual and emotional development and acknowledging their capacity for critical thinking. In addition, it is important to consider the long-term implications of censorship, as it can create a homogenous cultural landscape where certain perspectives are privileged, affecting individual children whose cultural identity is erased and, on a broader level, leading to a less informed and less critical populace (Hobbs, 2011).

3.7. Summary

This theoretical framework serves as the toolbox for the study of censorship in translated children's literature in Iran, utilizing the intersection of the concepts of cultural translation, cultural hegemony, reader-response theory, and developmental psychology. Each theory offers a unique lens through which the nuances censorship can be understood and its impact on children and their rights can be examined.

Cultural translation and cultural hegemony provide a foundation for understanding how translations are manipulated to align with specific ideological goals, helping elucidate the ways in which the Iranian authorities may use children's literature as a tool to perpetuate certain ideologies and suppress alternative narratives. Reader-response theory complements this by highlighting children's active role in meaning-making, which is critical in understanding children's interaction with censored materials and how such interactions influence their understanding of their own

rights. This theory suggests that even within the constraints of censorship, children are not passive recipients of information but are actively making sense of the messages they receive. Finally, developmental psychology offers insights into the broader implications of censorship on children's growth and development, underscoring the importance of diverse literary exposure for adolescents' well-rounded identity development and critical thinking skills. In synthesizing these theories, this framework helps achieve the objectives of the study, namely the answer to the questions of how censorship of translated children's literature in Iran occurs and is rationalized, as well as delving into its consequences for Iranian children.

Chapter 4: Methodology

The objective of this study is to explore the interplay between censorship, translation, and children's rights in the context of children's literature within the Islamic Republic of Iran, focusing in particular on adolescent readers' experiences and perceptions. More specifically, this study aims to explore how censorship of children's literature takes place under the current Iranian government and, subsequently, study the effects of this practice on adolescents and their rights. In the present chapter, the methodology employed to carry out this research is explained in detail. This chapter is structured to first introduce the research philosophy, followed by a detailed discussion of the research design and related methodological choices, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques. It concludes with an evaluation of the methodological limitations and ethical considerations.

4.1. Research Philosophy: An Interpretivist Approach

The goal of this research is to understand the complex phenomena of censorship of translated children's literature and its perceived impact on Iranian child readers and their rights. Furthermore, the focal interest is specific instances and lived experiences, as opposed to creating a generalized representative sample. In this context, knowledge is acquired in the process of meaning-making and is, thus, relative, resulting from the researcher and texts/participants' interactive relationship. In other words, for the scope of this study and based on its objectives, an interpretivist philosophical approach has been adopted to acquire more in-depth knowledge of individual cases and experiences. The study, therefore, focuses on narratives, stories, perceptions,

and interpretations in its epistemology (Goddard et al., 2004). Additionally, the epistemology could be considered transactional or subjectivist since, in the case of this research, individuals cannot be separated from their knowledge, resulting in a link between the researcher and the subjects, which in turn results in subjective interpretation of data.

Furthermore, the study follows a relativist ontology, perceiving reality intersubjectively, i.e., believing there to be multiple meanings, interpretations, and realities based on individual experiences and practices, and consequently, for the nature of reality to be socially constructed through culture and language (Saunders et al., 2012). As a result of these choices, the research methods applied here will be inductive, based on in-depth investigations with small samples, following qualitative methods of analysis to interpret data.

4.2. Research Design: Inductive Methods

As explained in 3.1., the aim of this research is to understand the dynamics of censorship in translated children's literature in Iran and its perceived impacts on children and their rights; therefore, a bottom-up inductive approach is best suited to achieve that goal, meaning that the research starts with gathering data and making observations, followed by using data to distinguish any patterns and theorize based on them (Goddard et al., 2004). In addition to the inductive method being the most suitable route in this research, this method is also often used in exploratory research where the existing body of research surrounding it is limited (Bernard, 2011). In such a context, inductive research can help add new data and ideas to the previous research.

4.2.1. Textual Analysis of Selected Titles

Using an inductive research approach, the first half of the study attempts to answer the question of how censorship in translated children's literature in Iran takes place, using detailed textual analysis of three selected titles in translation that have faced various forms of censorship before and after publication. The titles selected are J. K. Rowling's *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone* (1997), translated into Persian by Saeed Kebriaei and published by Ketaabsaraa-ye Tandis publishing house, Arthur Conan Doyle's *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes* (1892), translated into Persian by Maryam Ansari and published by E'tela-ye Vatan publishing house, and Dan Brown's *The Da Vinci Code* (2003), translated by Hossein Shahraabi and published by Ketaabsaraa-ye Tandis publishing house.

These books were chosen due to their global popularity and the censorship issues they have faced in Iran, from omission or alteration of certain words to the translated book being entirely banned by the Iranian Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance, making them ideal candidates for exploring the process and mechanisms of censorship in the case of translated children's literature, as well as the broader implications of this censorship for the young readers of these titles. The selection proved to be a practical and fruitful one since it was welcomed by participants who had positive reactions to the narratives and had formed their own opinions on matters related to these texts.

Furthermore, while various forms of censorship are employed both in these titles and on a bigger scale in general, for the purpose of this study, censorship of subjects dealing with religious matters is studied and analyzed. More specifically, censorship of topics that do not align with Islamic Sharia and are therefore considered inappropriate material by the Ministry is the focus of

the textual analysis. Utilizing the theoretical framework developed in chapter three and building on the previous research detailed in chapter 2, these three titles are analyzed from the lens of cultural hegemony and cultural translation studies, a process during which specific instances of religious censorship are listed and then analyzed in order to better understand the mechanisms of censorship in Iran.

4.2.2. Interviews with Iranian Youth

For the second part of this study, following the same path of inductive reasoning, an ethnographic research approach is chosen in order to capture the experiences and perceptions of participants in their natural environment. In other words, adolescents aged 15-17 years old were recruited through educational organizations or via acquaintances, who were then made aware of the scope and objectives of this research, after which 16 participants were selected to go forward based on their agreement with taking part in this research. These participants were then asked to read the Persian translation of the three selected titles to the best of their abilities; however, there was no strict requirement posed on them to complete reading these lengthy books in their entirety, since the aim of the study is to conduct authentic ethnographic research and examine children's perception of censorship in Iran in order to better understand its impact on them from their own perspective.

Following that, separate interviews were conducted with these 16 participants, who came from various educational and geographical backgrounds, as well as different religious orientations, in order to provide as diverse a dataset as possible considering the scope of the study and to reduce the potential of biased views based on children's socio-economic background, which could play a

role in their perception of the topic. More importantly, four participants identified as practising Muslims, while others stated that while born in Muslim families, they do not adhere to any particular religion; this proved to be an essential part of the study since religious censorship was being discussed and studied. Interviews were then conducted individually via the Google Meets platform, chosen for its accessibility without a VPN inside Iran. Prior to the interviews, detailed consent forms explaining the study's scope, purpose, and the nature of the questions, as well as information about the interviewer and contact details, were provided and signed by participants (Appendix 2) and their guardians (Appendix 3). To ensure an easy environment, participants were given the option to have a third person present with them during the interviews; three participants opted to have family members or friends present during the interviews, who also signed informed consent forms (Appendix 4) designed specifically for them.

The interview sessions were structured in an easy and informal manner and in children's native language (Persian, Achomi, and Luri) to make the environment as laidback as possible and provide the participants with the opportunity to be their authentic selves and express their opinions freely. As a result, the previously prepared list of interview questions (Appendix 1) was altered to fit each interviewee's style of discussion while at the same time attempting to cover all the necessary topics. The length of each interview differed slightly based on additional subjects that came up in participants' answers, but the general span of interviews was from 45 to 60 minutes. Each session was recorded in audio format with the participants' permission, acquired previously in consent forms, and less formally, at the beginning of the interview; these recordings were then transcribed and translated from Persian to English for detailed thematic analysis. All audio and text files only existed offline on a personal computer, and the original files were deleted after data anonymization to protect the participants' privacy and safety.

Data collection was designed to provide an in-depth look at teenagers' experience with censored literature. The interviews specifically focused on their observations of altered or omitted themes and content in the books they had read, as well as censorship they might have encountered in life on a larger scale. Questions were structured in a way that gave the interviewees the freedom to express their detailed responses, which, in turn, revealed their awareness and understanding of censorship and its implications for their rights as children. The transcription of these interviews will serve as the primary data source for this part of the research. Through thematic analysis, common themes and patterns, as well as notable differences in experiences and thoughts among participants, will be identified, taking into account the comparison of responses based on their religious orientations to assess any variations in the impact of censorship.

4.3. Methodological Limitations

The methodology chosen and employed in this study was meticulously designed to achieve depth and precision in exploring and answering the research questions; however, the study faced a number of limitations due to its scope and resources. Firstly, the research was constrained to an analysis of only three translated books, a limitation primarily dictated by time constraints. While this focus allowed for a detailed and thorough analysis of each text, it may also limit the generalizability of the findings. Nonetheless, the selection was intended to provide deep insights into the processes and implications of censorship rather than a superficial overview that would arise from a broader but less detailed approach. Secondly, the empirical component of the study was determined by the practical realities of conducting intensive interviews within a limited time frame available for the research. This approach, while facilitating a detailed exploration of

individual experiences and perceptions, resulted in a relatively small sample size with possibly limited ability to extrapolate the findings to a broader population.

Finally, the potential for bias should be considered in this study. As an Iranian researcher with a professional background in translation, my close connection to the context of the study might influence the interpretation of the data and the selection of literature; however, this insider perspective could also prove beneficial for understanding subtle nuances and cultural contexts, which could be lost to an individual not sufficiently familiar with the context of the research. Through proper methodological choices such as choosing a qualitative, interpretivist approach, these methodological limitations and their ensuing challenges were acknowledged and addressed within the research design to maintain the integrity and depth of the results of the study in order to add value to the existing literature on the subject despite the stated limitations.

4.4. Ethical Considerations

As previously elaborated on in 4.2.2., ethical compliance was maintained in all stages of the research. Due to the sensitive subject of the study, it was essential to make participants and their guardians thoroughly informed on the scope of the study and its objectives, making sure that they were aware of all the implications and felt safe in proceeding with their participation. Informed consent was then obtained from all participants and accompanying parties after thorough explanation of the research and answering any ensuing questions. To protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants, all personally identifiable information such as name, location, and references to real people and places were removed from the transcriptions, with the

anonymized transcriptions only accessible to the researcher and terminated after the completion of the research.

In conclusion, this chapter has outlined the methodological framework used to investigate the censorship of translated children's literature in Iran, starting with elaborating on the philosophy behind methodological choices. Next, the research design was explained in detail, including a two-part research approach of textual analysis coupled with individual interviews. Finally, potential limitations and ethical considerations were included to complete the chapter.

Chapter 5: Textual Analysis of Selected Texts

In order to explore how censorship of Iranian children's literature through translation takes place, three widely recognized titles were selected for textual analysis: *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone* (1997) by J. K. Rowling, *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes* (1892) by Sir Arthur Conan Doyle, and *The Da Vinci Code* (2003) by Dan Brown. This chapter details how censorship manifests differently in each work by direct comparison of the English and Persian versions of the texts in the first two titles, a process during which it is important to understand the function of omissions in censor-oriented translations. Here, omissions are deliberate acts to exclude certain content that may be deemed inappropriate or threatening to sociopolitical norms and values of the target culture (Tymoczko, 2002) –in the case of this study, content in conflict with religion– which often results in a dilution or alteration of the themes, characters, and messages present in the original narratives, thus shaping the reader's perception in line with the dominant ideology (Toury, 1995). However, in the case of the third title, censorship is analyzed by looking at the events surrounding the publication of the Persian translation, i.e., the official banning by the Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance.

This chapter starts by first elaborating on how the first title, *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone* has undergone numerous small omissions and alterations of subjects that are forbidden according to Islamic Sharia and country's laws, moving on to the second title, *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, that has three full stories excluded from the Persian translation due to their conceivably inappropriate narratives according to Islam, in addition to other minor omissions and alterations that are similar in nature to those of the first title. Finally, the chapter investigates censorship in the case of the third title, *The Da Vinci Code*, which has faced an altogether unique form of censorship compared to the other two, with the translated version getting banned due to

its offensive content toward religion and religious communities in Iran. This close reading of each text is then followed by a concluding section examining and elaborating on the dynamics behind these censorship choices and potential implications for the landscape of Iranian children's literature.

5.1. Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone

The Persian translation of *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone* by Saeed Kebriaei for Ketabsaraa-ye Tandis Publishing House provides clear examples of censorship, mainly through omission. The following are some of the notable instances:

In the first instance, the affectionate gesture of Mr. Dursley toward his wife is omitted. More specifically, the sentence "Mr. Dursley pecked Mrs. Dursley on the cheek" (Rowling, 1997, p.2) is completely omitted in the Persian translation. Similarly, Hermione's affection for Harry in the line "Hermione looked ready to fling her arms around him again, but Harry was glad she held herself in as his head was still very sore" (Rowling, 1997, p.240), is absent in the Persian translation. These decisions are to comply with the Ministry's regulations that any content not aligning with Sharia (in this case, physical displays of affection between opposite genders) should not be available to the general public (Selgi, 2016). While the first instance does not explicitly fit into this rule, it is perhaps omitted due to the laws of the country that limit displays of affection between couples to private settings (Islamic Penal Code of Iran, art. 637).

A more common instance is the omission of any mentions of alcoholic beverages or characters being under the influence of alcohol. Toward the end of the first chapter, where people are described as "holding up their glasses and saying in hushed voices: 'To Harry Potter – the boy

who lived!” (Rowling, 1997, p. 13), the phrase “holding up their glasses” is omitted, and the exclamation is changed to “long live Harry Potter – the boy who lived!” In addition, in the second chapter, the phrase “Aunt Petunia had to run and get him a large brandy” (Rowling, 1997, p. 26) is removed from the Persian translation. Finally, in chapter four, Hagrid's request for a strong drink, “I’d not say no ter summat stronger if yeh’ve got it, mind”, as well as the scene where “Harry watched Hagrid getting redder... as he called for more wine” (Rowling, 1997, p. 166) and its playful aftermath of Hagrid kissing Professor McGonagall on the cheek are excluded in their entirety, which is another instance of omission of physical display of affection. Other references to alcohol, such as Hagrid’s visit to a bar for a “pick-me-up” (Rowling, 1997, p. 66) are similarly erased, as is an entire setting where “old women were sitting... drinking tiny glasses of sherry... one of them was smoking a long pipe” (Rowling, 1997, P.58), cutting out both smoking and drinking elements.

The omission of references to alcohol consumption is due to its being forbidden in Islam and consequently, completely illegal in Iran, resulting in the subject being one of the most common areas targeted by the Ministry’s screening sector (Selgi, 2016). The Ministry justifies this decision by the fact that according to official – yet vastly inaccurate, according to recent surveys (Tamimi Arab et al., 2020)– statistics, more than 99% of the Iranian population are Muslims who would not prefer to be exposed to such subjects. However, this is in contrast to the official statistics by the Iranian Ministry of Health and Medical Education, which claims approximately 420,000,000 litres of alcoholic drinks are illegally sold and consumed in Iran per year (Persian BBC News, 2023). This demonstrates that the Iranian population and their children are familiar with this subject, and a considerable number of them who do not identify as Muslims do not object to alcoholic beverages being mentioned in media they consume.

Finally, the omission of the mention of old women sitting around and smoking on page 58 signals a deeper and perhaps more unofficial system that remains vague to translators, publishers, and the audience of published books alike. While smoking is not illegal in Iran for women, it is heavily frowned upon (Inanloo, 2023) and, thus, deemed inappropriate for publishing. On a deeper level, however, it could be argued that this is one of the ways the Iranian authorities utilize cultural oppression in order to promote certain ideologies, including the oppression and erasure of Iranian women in society, believing feminism to be a Western and misleading product that goes against Islam (Hosseini, 2009), and limiting women's presence in society to their domestic gender roles.

5.2. The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes

In the case of *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, translated by Maryam Ansari for Etelāye Vatan Publishing House, three stories were excluded from the Persian version in their entirety: *A Scandal in Bohemia*, *The Adventure of the Noble Bachelor*, and *A Case of Identity*. The three of these stories revolve around themes of intimate relationships, romantic affairs outside of marriage, infidelity, and other such topics that may be considered as inappropriate for children of certain cultural backgrounds and religions.

These exclusions are in addition to mentions of alcoholic beverages being omitted from the text, similar to instances in 5.1., and are the main focus of this section. *A Scandal in Bohemia*, due to its plot containing mentions of relationships outside of marriage, in addition to its main character being an independent and nontraditional woman, has been excluded from the Persian translation by the translator to get publishing permission from the Ministry. Similarly, after undergoing the screening process, the other two mentioned stories were also deemed inappropriate

due to their undertones of infidelity and relationship outside of marriage and were omitted altogether by the editor in order to get legal approval for publication. In this case, the censors' notes mentioned that "these are not appropriate for children. We don't have such a culture, and we don't need to introduce these Western ideas to our children. We advise that you omit them before we proceed with the next step."

As the translator of this title and, generally, a translator familiar with the Ministry's regulations, I did not anticipate the exclusion of these two stories since they do not explicitly violate any Islamic laws; however, this instance further sheds light on the ambiguity of the rules and regulations set in place by the Ministry that seem to fluctuate during each president's time in the office, and remain vague for translators and the general public. In the presence of such ambiguity, the government can use various censorship measures as tools to erase certain narratives and further promote others.

5.3. The Da Vinci Code

Among the three titles, Dan Brown's *The Da Vinci Code*, translated by Hossein Shahrabi and published by Ketabsaraa-ye Tandis, could be said to have faced the most severe form of censorship, which was a complete public ban in 2006, a few months after its initial publication, due to objections from Christian communities in Iran, and further support from the Muslim population (Persian BBC News, 2006). Despite these measures, the availability of the title in unofficial outlets (e.g., street vendors) and e-book format on platforms such as Fidibo, Iran's largest e-book distributor, as well as in physical form in the limited number of bookstores that stock foreign books, suggests a more complex reality. In other words, this dichotomy in the

accessibility of the book points to a potential dissonance in the practice of censorship, raising questions about the sincerity of the authorities' intentions in enforcing these bans, suggesting that such measures may serve as more of a demonstration of ideological enforcement under the guise of protecting religious and moral sensibilities than as effective cultural protection.

5.4. Concluding Thoughts

This chapter has conducted a textual analysis of the three titles chosen for this study. From subtle omissions to outright bans, the patterns of censorship reflect both legal and cultural constraints imposed by Iranian authorities. While claimed to be with the intention of safeguarding societal values, these censorship measures raise questions about their effectiveness and the real motivations behind them—whether they genuinely aim to protect community morals or serve to enforce political ideology under the guise of moral guardianship. Finally, these inconsistencies and ambiguities in the application and enforcement of censorship demonstrate that such practices not only suppress diverse narratives but can also foster a culture of circumvention and scepticism among readers, which will be thoroughly examined in the next chapter, in addition to other nuanced impacts of censorship on the young readers.

Chapter 6: Interview with Iranian Youth, Results and Interpretations

As the second part of this research, this chapter examines in detail how censorship in translation impacts Iranian youth's perception of their reading experience and their rights as children. This is done via interviews where participants' awareness of content omissions and alterations in the three selected titles and their reactions to them were assessed, in addition to their thoughts and feelings regarding the impact of these changes on their rights as children and their perceptions of the practice of censorship in general.

6.1. Initial Thoughts and Observations

During the initial stages of planning interviews, participants were asked to read the three selected titles for this study. By the time of the interviews, all had read the *Harry Potter* book, while thirteen had read the *Sherlock Holmes* stories, and only five had managed to read *The Da Vinci Code* due to its limited availability in Iran. Participants were first asked two questions on their initial general thoughts and observations reading the Persian translation of the three texts, J. K. Rowling's *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone*, Arthur Conan Doyle's *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, and Dan Brown's *The Da Vinci Code*, followed up by a question about whether the content of the books seemed incomplete or edited to them at all.

Participants responded to the first question mostly with positive excitement toward the narratives and found the stories in general to be interesting and good reading material; however, there were seven instances (participants 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 15, 16) where the participants had heard of

omissions having taken place in these books from either their friends who had read the original text, watched the movies and TV shows, or simply through word of mouth, e.g., it being common knowledge that drinking is censored in all texts (Selgi, 2016). Their answers were, in general, similar to that of participant 13, who put it quite concisely as, “well, I guess everyone has heard of some kind of screening or censorship, especially in Western books and TV shows.”

In other words, these examples were found outside the text rather than during the reading experience. This could potentially speak of a reading culture and environment in which censorship is talked about, and stories about censorship circulate. This general awareness of censorship as an existing practice in society could lead to the young readers’ lack of trust in texts available in translation, which has been previously studied in Iranian adults, with the results showing that readers have lost their trust in books published in Iran due to the strong possibility of pre-publishing censorship (Yahyapour, 2015). If children bring this lack of trust to their experience of reading a text, this could result in a different response to the text, which, in turn, leads to a different process of meaning-making where the potential of altered or omitted information affects the young reader’s understanding of the narrative and their feeling toward the experience of reading and the text itself (Tyson, 2006). This effect could manifest negatively as children’s scepticism toward the practice of reading or could alternatively result in children’s hyper-awareness of censorship, both of which alter the children’s reading experience—the following results further cement this possibility.

A total number of six participants (1, 4, 7, 9, 10, 14) had watched the movies or series for at least one of the titles and were aware of material present in the shows that was missing from the Persian texts. For instance, participant 9, who had watched the downloaded, unofficially subtitled version of the *Harry Potter* movies but had not previously read the books, mentioned that “I guess

it's not that essential to the story, but I always think of Hagrid as someone who likes drinking... I think it's part of his character, right? So, it's weird to not have it mentioned at all." Similar to participant 9, other participants in this group of six expressed a vague sense of confusion in their reaction to censorship. In other words, they seemed—at least partially—aware of the justification behind it, but did not fully understand the reason, e.g., they knew of the Ministry's regulations but did not think there was anything wrong with mentions of alcohol (mainly in the case of *Harry Potter*) or infidelity (in the case of *Sherlock Holmes*). As a result, in addition to the practice of censorship impacting their approach to reading, being informed about censorship in the media they consume, coupled with the confusion exhibited by the participants in their reactions to said censorship, could have a significant impact on the children's development of a sense of identity.

To elaborate, following Erikson's stages of development, adolescence is a stage in which one's sense of identity is developed. More specifically, during this period, children explore their independence and autonomy and develop a sense of self (Bishop, 2013). Censorship in literature interferes with this process by restricting access to diverse ideas and perspectives, which are essential for broadening adolescents' understanding of the world and themselves. When themes such as romance, alcohol consumption, or independent female characters are omitted, it limits the opportunity for young readers to engage with subjects outside of their immediate cultural conventions. Furthermore, in the context of this study, these participants' reaction to and experience of censorship could potentially affect their perceived independence, leading to a lack of feelings of independence and control. Consequently, this restriction can result in role confusion or a weaker sense of self, as adolescents are deprived of the necessary experiences to fully explore and define their identities.

Besides their awareness of altered or omitted content, participants 7 and 10 also found the practice to be degrading regarding the children's autonomy as well as their cognitive development and their resulting knowledge of the world at large. About this, participant 7, who had similarly watched the *Harry Potter* movies, explained: "I mean what even is the point? It's not like we don't know what alcohol is! It's very common, too! We're not children anymore, I find it insulting to be honest... like I can't decide what to read or not!" Following the Neo-Kohlbergian Schema Model by Rest and colleagues (2000) regarding these participants (7 and 10), it can be inferred that they have attained the Postconventional Schema in their moral codes, signalling a mindset where the adolescent considers moral ideas and principles, and can decide on the right or wrong based on their own knowledge and judgment, rather than society's conventions. In other words, these children find themselves capable of making the decision of what text to read and find the current censorship practice oppressive to their autonomy as informed humans living in the society.

Finally, three participants (1, 10, 14) were previously fans of these franchises and had accessed detailed information regarding the instances of censorship and were meticulously aware of them. This had led them to not trust the Persian texts as a reliable source of information and instead rely on online platforms or original texts for accurate data. For instance, participant 1 explained that they are "a member of Sherlock fan groups on Telegram [messenger app] and follow fan pages on Instagram." When asked if these are credible sources, they elaborated that "they're more for gathering and discussing ideas and fan theories—for the uncensored story itself we just download the episodes with subtitles."

This level of acute awareness shown by said participants has led to a notable response by them as readers of these texts. The participants' choice to turn to online platforms or original texts illustrates a subtle and perhaps unconscious form of resistance against the presence of cultural

hegemony in Iran, where the post-Revolution government might be exerting control over the available narratives by using literature as a means to further instil a homogeneous ideology (Adamson, 2014). The children's knowledge of these omissions and modifications in the translated text, coupled with their exposure to film adaptations or the original versions, has led them to mistrust the censored texts. Through the lens of transactional reader-response theory, this response indicates a dynamic transaction where during these young readers' interaction with the texts, they are not passive recipients of information but active participants in constructing meaning (Tyson, 2006). Their scepticism and the resulting search for uncensored material show their active role in reshaping the perceived credibility and authenticity of the texts. This engagement could represent a form of reader empowerment, i.e., young readers pushing back against the state's attempts to control their reading experience and, by extension, their worldview.

Therefore, the distrust exhibited by the participants can be viewed as a form of rebellion against the government's control of narratives, signalling a shift where young readers are challenging the boundaries of imposed knowledge. This pattern in the participants' response to texts hints at a change in how narratives are perceived in the context of state-imposed censorship, making the child readers active meaning-makers instead of passive recipients of text.

6.2. Specifics on Omissions and Changes

In the next step, participants were asked more detailed questions regarding these omissions and changes for each book separately. In a number of the interviews, these three questions were tied to the first section and were answered together; however, for the sake of organization, the answers will be elaborated on separately.

6.2.1. Censorship in the Persian Translation of *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone*

Participants did not show any signs of being surprised with the zero-tolerance policy toward alcoholic beverages or instances of characters being drunk in the case of *Harry Potter*, since alcohol is forbidden according to Islamic Sharia and therefore legally banned in Iran; however, as mentioned in 5.1., this was followed with a sense of confusion over the justification for said censorship. In other words, as quoted from participant 7's response, the children did not seem to deem such censorship necessary or useful for their protection. Nevertheless, the omission of mentions of alcohol is a common aspect of censorship practices in the country (Selgi, 2016), and in fact, a few of the participants (1, 2, 10, 12, 15) found the rigidity around such a 'trivial' topic to be entertaining and/or funny. In addition, they seemed to find this a small issue compared to what could be censored and, as a result, potentially change or take away from the story. On the other hand, however, this did add to the children's lack of trust in officially published texts that were present throughout their answers.

6.2.2. Censorship in The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes

In the case of the *Sherlock Holmes* stories, the exclusion of *A Scandal in Bohemia* was particularly noted by the two participants (1 and 14), who were avid fans of the series and found the omission a disappointment. Furthermore, while they were aware of why such a story with undertones of infidelity and relationship outside of marriage would be censored in the Persian translation and could not get publishing permission from the Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance, the organization in charge of censorship regulations (Selgi, 2016), they did not find the practice any more rational than omitting mentions of drinking alcohol.

In this regard, participant 1, who had previously read an older translation of the *Sherlock Holmes* stories, stated: “to be honest, I hadn’t thought of it—that they’d exclude the *Scandal*, but I guess it’s the logical way, no?” When asked what they meant by the term ‘logical’, and if that was their own logic, they replied: “No, I mean [the Ministry’s] logic. It’s expected of them.” Participant 14, another fan of the *Sherlock Holmes* franchise who had watched the series but was reading the book for the first time, reacted in a similar way, explaining that “I saw it for the first time when I downloaded the subtitled series¹ from [Persian illegal movie platform]. I mean, I think it’s such an important story, but then again, it was also censored from the show...with the whole mysterious independent woman vibes, I guess it makes sense.” In addition, this participant emphasized the role of a female main character in the story’s exclusion: “when you look at the state of women in the country... with everything that’s been happening, it makes sense that the Ministry wouldn’t want young girls reading such a story.” When asked to elaborate, participant 14 responded: “it’s almost a feminist story, no? They don’t like feminism.”

The comments point to the fact that these children are well informed about censorship practices in the media they consume but do not necessarily agree with them or the logic behind the regulations, and again, turn to online and original sources for uncensored information about their favourite stories. Furthermore, the participants thought the present state of censorship was so obvious that they had to be asked to elaborate on their comments. However, this awareness took a turn in the case of the next title, *The Da Vinci Code*, which will be discussed in the following subsection.

¹ To prevent any potential confusion regarding the mention of adaptations in discussing censored material, it should be noted that some participants integrated their reading of these books with their previous experience of viewing adaptations in the form of television series and films.

6.2.3. Censorship of the Persian Translation of *The Da Vinci Code*

As for *The Da Vinci Code*, twelve participants (2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16) were confused about the reason the translation of this title was banned, while the rest (1, 5, 7, 14) had heard of the controversy surrounding its content that was deemed to be insulting to Christianity and resulted in its complete ban just a few months after initial publication. Since the book is still - illegally and on an unofficial level- available in Iran, and since the English version is legally found in bookstores, participants did not understand the issue and were not aware of it.

Participant 5 noted “I think it’s been banned for so long that people our age don’t even know it, right? I just see it all the time in the street vendors’ banned books [section], so I guessed it must’ve been banned.” This answer is significant in that it shows there is no official source for children to become aware of the banning and censorship of texts that should be available to them. Furthermore, it is important to mention that street vendors who sell banned books, as well as bookshops selling original English texts, are only found in major cities in Iran, which could be a reason why only a number of participants were aware of this issue.

While the answers to other questions are, for the most part, not easily categorized, in the case of this title, the majority of the participants who were not previously aware of the ban reacted along two specific lines when the reason behind the translated book’s banning was explained to them. The first group that makes up the majority (participants 2, 3, 4, 10, 12, 13, 15) were children who were not practising Muslims, and their viewpoints did not show signs of any religious orientation. From this group, participant 13 responded with the resigned response of, “well, what do you expect? They don’t even allow [mentions of] drinking. This is a more dangerous topic... It’s an Islamic country.” This feeling of resignation was echoed in a number of other participants

throughout the interview as well, who expressed their feelings with a similar attitude of “What do you expect?” and “It is what it is.”

In contrast, participant 6, a practising Muslim, responded that “Well, it makes sense then. I didn’t read the book since it was banned, but now that I know what the story is about...” When asked to elaborate on how the subject of the book merits its banning, they explained: “It’s offensive to people’s Holy beliefs. I just think some things shouldn’t be so easily available or read at all.” The answers from other Muslim participants (8, 9, 11, 16) showed varying degrees of the same concern over the book’s offensive content in a Muslim community. It appears that this text’s perceived offensiveness to religion had caused a shift in the participants’ reactions to its banning. In other words, participants seemed to consider the subject a more sensitive one and, consequently, deserving of censorship in the context of the Islamic Republic of Iran. This ambivalence regarding censorship practices was also echoed in later sections of the interview, hinting at either children’s confusion or, in contrast, their nuanced understanding of the topic.

6.3. Perceptions of Censorship and Children’s Rights

The following four questions aimed to gather the participants’ knowledge and perception of censorship and the ways in which this practice may affect their rights as a young reader and, how that, in turn, makes them feel about the topic in general. The unanimous reaction to the first question on what they understand about the term ‘censorship’, was that while all participants were aware of censorship as a common practice that exists in Iran, not all of them knew about it in the context of children’s literature in particular.

In response to the question asking participants for their definition of censorship and instances of it they might have in mind, the participants mainly formed their definitions around examples from their own lived experiences. In other words, their understanding of censorship differed from the academic viewpoint outlined in the Theoretical Framework chapter in that the children's definition was based on instances they had encountered in real-life situations and in practice rather than being based on theoretical concepts. It appears that those who were more actively involved in reading translated texts outside of the school curriculum (participants 1, 4, 7, 10, 14) were aware of censorship in those texts (e.g., participant 14 turned to online platforms for the original content), while the others perceived it in general as something belonging to the world of cinema and provided examples from that area, which is perhaps a more common and visible practice and also more widely discussed within the context of Iran (Naficy, 1995; Taheri, 2024).

To elaborate on this point, in the case of censorship in cinema, most foreign movies are not screened in Iranian cinemas with the rest of the world or are only shown after they have been approved by the Ministry of Culture, dubbed into Persian (Ayoubi, 2017), and potentially undergone censorship, or more commonly, scenes being cut off halfway through from movies, or perhaps most visible of all, female figures' skin and hair being covered through CGI. These instances were also mentioned by the participants, with participant 15 recalling that they "remember when in *Shrek* [2001] movie, the kissing scene [was] so awkwardly cut-off in the TV version [that is officially broadcasted] that it was funny," and participant 13 providing another example of censorship in cinema: "In Iranian shows, women have their hair covered even when they go to bed, or when they're at home with their families!"

In addition to cinema, the censorship of news in national channels was noted by a number of participants in the definitions and examples of censorship. Participant 13 defined censorship as

“when the government censors something so people don’t see it. Like in the news on TV [referring to national TV that is legally accessed inside the country], or when they omit sex scenes from movies.” This response was echoed by some other participants as well, who were aware of the censorship practised by the Iranian government in different aspects of their daily lives.

In another instance, participant 15 said with a chuckle, “They don’t call it censorship. It’s ‘auditing’. I guess it’s just when something is hidden from people? Like in our English textbook, they have very obviously covered women’s arms and chests with black. It’s badly Photoshopped, too! It’s kind of humiliating...” These instances (and the ones provided by other participants of this group) speak of a culture in which censorship is encountered in children’s daily lives at home or in school, and all children can easily recall moments of it, even if they are not sure of the logic or process behind it. In fact, a considerable lack of emphasis on the rationale behind these examples was noted here, with the children having grown up in a culture promoting censorship as a normal practice that just exists. Having an array of lived experiences with censorship further instils the children’s aforementioned lack of trust in translated texts. This lack of trust could at times work as a double-edged sword since it motivates the children to seek out accurate data and, in this process, develop critical thinking and show an active resistance against authoritarian practices, while on the other hand, it hinders their adequate development of identity, resulting in their pessimism and perceived lack of control over other aspects of their lives (Bishop, 2013).

6.4. Censorship and Children’s Rights: Opinions

In the next part of the interview, when asked about how this censorship practice might affect their rights as a young reader, five participants (2, 5, 7, 10, 15) were more vocal about the

issue compared to others and believed that censorship deprives them of the chance to freely experience a text in its full scope. In this regard, participant 15 stated: “Yes, I think it has a negative effect on our rights; it’s obvious. Our rights are denied in so many other areas, right? I don’t even have the right to dress how I want! Or like, my dad didn’t want to vote in the last election, but had to, otherwise he’d be harassed about it by his boss in the [governmental] office. So, this is just another one of those areas, I guess.”

Such instances of the authorities’ breach of Iranian people’s rights were present in the four other participants’ (2, 5, 7, 10) answers as well, which shows a remarkable awareness of their political environment and happenings outside of rules and practices directly affecting them. Therefore, their more active engagement in this matter may be traced back to their general political awareness, in addition to being informed and holding autonomous opinions in socio-political matters that came up in the course of the interviews, which in turn could result from being in families where political matters are discussed more often, and children are more involved in such discussions.

As for the rest of the participants (1, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16), it seemed that it was not a topic they had previously given much thought to or were given any explicit information about, except their own personal experiences and word of mouth surrounding texts that had undergone censorship. In addition, it seemed that the majority of children considered the concept of rights to belong to ‘more serious’ topics, as some participants (1, 4, 14, 16) put it. For instance, participant 14 stated: “I mean... for me, *Sherlock* is very important, but I think it’s not that important compared to other more serious stuff. Like, they are arresting, torturing, killing teenagers, so what’s a little bit of censorship?” Similarly, participant 16 explained: “to be honest I hadn’t thought of it as something impacting my rights. Like, you know, so many other laws exist

in Iran that deny people more serious stuff—the laws that cost people their lives! So, censorship wasn't that big of a deal.” Such comments are notable in that they speak of a relative awareness of censorship; in other words, most participants did not consider censorship to be a significant issue until prompted by the interviewer, which could suggest that for many children in restrictive environments, censorship has become normalized. As developmental psychology posits that adolescents tend to put more focus and emphasis on immediate, tangible aspects of their environments rather than on abstract concepts like their rights (Mcleod, 2024), this focus may lead them to overlook the implications of a normalized practice of censorship.

Furthermore, these comments illustrate how children may prioritize their concerns based on the severity of the perceived threats around them. In a society where more extreme violations of human rights are common, censorship of literature might seem trivial and/or secondary. The concept of ‘serious’ issues, as articulated by participants, reflects a maturity in understanding the gravity of different societal issues but also a compartmentalization that might be influenced by their developmental stage as adolescents who are beginning to form complex views of societal structures but might still prioritize issues based on direct impact or visible outcomes (Piaget, 1964). Additionally, this group of participants’ comments suggests a cultural context in which the concept of individual human rights, particularly related to freedom of expression in this case, is not emphasized or is overshadowed by more immediate survival concerns, which aligns with the notion that cultural and societal contexts shape individuals’ understanding and valuation of abstract concepts like rights (Vygotsky, 1978).

Finally, from the perspective of cultural hegemony, these responses also indicate how state practices may influence people’s perceptions of what is considered normal or serious. When a government’s actions condition its people to accept or expect certain infringements on their

freedom, these practices –in this case, the practice of censorship– can become embedded in the cultural fabric as less significant (Adamson, 2014). Gramsci’s theory further suggests that societal control is achieved not only through force, but also through the shaping of norms and values (Hoare et al., 2005). In the context of this study, the normalization of more overt human rights violations (e.g., physical violence) makes less overt forms of control (such as censorship) seem less oppressive or noteworthy.

Regardless of children’s opinions on how seriously their rights are impacted by censorship in texts they encounter, when prompted, all participants voiced that censorship is, in fact, an infringement on their rights to have free access to media, that it may affect their inclination to pick up a translated book, and that it makes it hard to trust the text they are reading. However, it is worth noting that while stating that censorship can be considered a violation of children’s rights, participants 6, 8, 9, 11, and 16 nevertheless found it necessary to be protected from inappropriate material. These five participants’ approaches regarding their view on censorship appeared to be perhaps slightly contradictory. On one hand, they identified themselves as practising Muslims, who consequently had to respect and adhere to the Islamic Sharia, which resulted in them finding issues with certain material’s availability in a Muslim society ². At the same time, however, as mentioned in the previous paragraph, they all stated in different words that, in their opinion, making a book available in a censored format is not the right approach to moderating content.

When asked if they had any alternative solutions, one participant (8) suggested creating enough awareness around books so that children and their guardians can choose whether to select that text as appropriate reading material or not. In another instance, participant 6 stated: “Why

² It should be noted here that according to a 2020 online anonymous survey by the GAMAAN Institute (The Group for Analyzing and Measuring Attitudes in IRAN) based in the Netherlands, only around 40% of the identified as Muslims, in contrast to the government’s official statistics of 99.5% (Tamimi Arab et al., 2020).

would they allow such a book [referring to the Persian translation of *Harry Potter*] to be published in the first place? I don't think all the magical tales are beneficial for us... and there are so many better books. When censorship is so common, I'm not sure what to read, you know? I don't know what is untouched." Participant 11 was similarly frustrated with the books being available to teenagers and explained that they "just think that's not the best content you could spend your time with... I'm not completely against their publishing, but maybe there should be a warning or something." Both of these participants further explained that publishing censored books is similar to the act of lying, which is one of the deadly sins in Islam and, therefore, not an appropriate practice for an Islamic government.

This was echoed by participant 16 in less direct words, but adding the fact that this existing form of censorship is affecting the credibility and popularity of religion negatively, explaining that "when they are censoring everything from news to children's toys like Barbie so irrationally and excessively in the name of Islam, they're just making us look bad. I don't think they even actually care about Islam anymore. They're just using it for their benefit." This critique that censorship is used manipulatively under the guise of religion may suggest a sophisticated level of critical engagement with societal structures, indicative of a shift towards Postconventional Schema (Rest et al., 2000); in other words, these participants engage in critical thinking and have developed their own set of moral codes beyond the societal conventions or the governmental laws. However, another interpretation would be that these five participants exhibit a sort of cognitive dissonance in their view of censorship, which would lead to the same conclusion about their development of critical thinking abilities.

On one hand, they tend to stick with their Islamic orientations that dictate certain material as improper, but on the other hand, they are in a stage of development where they can engage in

critical thinking (Piaget, 1964) and decide that censorship is an infringement on their rights. As cognitive dissonance prompts one to strive to align their beliefs with their actions (Harmon-Jones, 2019), these comments may signal the shaping of their moral reasoning considering censorship, i.e., they stay firm in their beliefs but also find the current practice of censorship to be problematic.

Additionally, this group's answers could hint at a form of self-imposed censorship –on levels varying from not publishing certain books at all, to providing warnings on the potentially inappropriate content of a book– meaning while recognizing the broader infringements of censorship, they advocate for a degree of protective filtering based on their religious and cultural beliefs, which they perceive to be different from the current state of censorship. This internal contradiction demonstrates a deeper layer of self-censorship, where children voluntarily endorse some level of restriction on their information consumption to align with personal or societal values. In other words, this self-censorship is not enforced by external authorities but is a personal choice driven by the participants' moral and ethical standards.

6.5. Censorship and Children's Rights: Emotions

As for how participants felt about censorship in the books they had read for this study or the books they encounter in their daily lives, reactions were in lines of frustration, resignation and acceptance. While the more vocal participants mentioned above (2, 5, 7, 10, 15) expressed their frustration, the majority (participants 1, 3, 4, 6, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16) seemed to face the issue with resignation and an it-is-what-it-is attitude, accepting that censorship exists and stating that there is not anything they can do about it. This acceptance of censorship reflects a form of learned helplessness, in which repeated exposure to uncontrollable events may lead one to believe that

they lack the power to change their circumstances (Peterson et al., 1995). This psychological state is particularly significant in a context like Iran, where pervasive censorship is normalized and rationalized by governmental authorities, ingraining a sense of futility among the children regarding their capability to influence such entrenched systems.

From the perspective of cultural hegemony, the feeling expressed by children in response to censorship could speak of a community in which children's literature has become a vehicle for instilling state-approved narratives and, thus, marginalizing the young readers and their autonomy in encountering and understanding alternative perspectives. This systemic control can diminish their agency and position them as marginal participants in their own cultural and literary landscapes. Furthermore, the resignation expressed by this group of participants toward censorship reflects not only their acceptance of this cultural hegemony but also their internalized understanding of their roles as passive recipients of literature. Their response signals a constrained engagement with texts, a process during which their interpretive freedom is limited by the content that is made available to them. This constrained interaction can, in turn, stifle the development of critical thinking that is happening at this stage of children's lives (McLeod, 2024).

In addition to these observations, becoming aware of the censorship (or the possibility of it) in translated books had caused disillusionment in some of the children, especially among the avid readers (1, 4, 7, 10, 14) or fans of these franchises (1,10, 14), resulting in them not trusting the translated versions of texts, and in some instances, resulting in an increase in their interest in learning English so they can have access to the original text (1, 2, 5, 7, 10, 14). For instance, as previously mentioned in 5.1., participant 1 preferred to stick with the subtitled *Sherlock* series to avoid potential censorship. In another instance, when asked about how they approach reading in their current context, participant 7 stated: "I'm very sceptical toward books that are being

published now... I mean, for movies and such, you kind of know for sure that they're going to be censored, so you just stick to the subbed version, but with books it's harder. So, I try to read the English text, even though it probably takes longer and may be difficult.”

Participant 10 similarly explained: “If you're a serious reader, if you really like a story, reading the [translated] Farsi books is just mentally difficult, you know?” When asked to elaborate as to what they mean by ‘mentally difficult’, they continued: “I mean that it's tiring to constantly look for omitted bits, I just don't trust the text, so it kind of ruins the fun... So, my friends and I took additional [extracurricular] English classes, so we could just read the main thing... Now I don't need to wait for Farsi translations... I also don't have to force myself to read censored books.” These responses may pose a contrast to the previously analyzed feeling of being resigned and accepting of the present censorship and was observed mainly in participants whose predominant emotional response toward the practice of censorship was frustration rather than acceptance or other reactions that could be perceived as passive. It could be this very frustration with the state of censorship that initially led them to take steps in order to resist the practice by seeking alternative sources of information.

In other words, these participants' behaviour might provide insights into the broader implications of censorship in authoritarian states. It illustrates a consciousness among young people about their rights to information and freedom of expression. Moreover, their ensuing actions reflect a broader trend where access to the internet and foreign language skills provide young people with more free access to global cultures and narratives, potentially undermining state efforts to control the flow of culture and information.

In essence, the disillusionment with censored texts among Iranian youth and their strategic move towards original English texts are not only acts of defiance but also indicative of broader

cognitive and psychological growth. Their actions exemplify how cultural and state-imposed limitations can act as catalysts for personal and collective transformations and, in turn, hint at the complex interplay between individual agency and structural constraints. To elaborate, this shift could be identified as a type of informal learning where individuals acquire knowledge and skills outside of formal educational settings and based on the learner's needs and goals, and which can lead to profound personal and professional growth (Marsick et al., 2002). In the case of our participants, motivated by a desire for uncensored information, they have taken the initiative to learn a new language and seek out original sources of information.

These individual actions, while seemingly focused on personal needs, have broader societal implications, as they hint at a potential cultural transformation within Iran, where the emerging generations value transparency, authenticity, and autonomy over moral and religious conventions. Such transformations could be pivotal in fostering societal openness and dialogue and potentially leading to a more democratic government and freer society in the future.

6.6. Broader Views on Censorship

In the next set of three questions, the attempt was to gather children's broader views on censorship, starting with how common they think censorship of literature in Iran is and how it might impact their access to a wide variety of texts and their embedded ideas. While these questions were answered in the other sections as well, it is necessary to reiterate the participants' answers here.

The participants were all aware of censorship happening on varying levels, from pre-publishing alterations to post-publishing banning; however, many participants (3, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12,

13, 15, and 16) thought of it as something belonging to content targeted at adults, or for cinema, which suffers more visible acts of censorship (Naficy, 1995). Censorship of youth literature was not thought of or known to be a common practice. In general, the answers to this set of questions, instances of which were previously mentioned in this chapter, revolved around the participants' beliefs that content should be moderated to ensure high quality and proper material but that the current state of censorship was too restrictive and irrational, which as teenagers they found annoying, since they felt powerless against the phenomenon. They also expressed confusion over the ambiguity of what gets censored and what does not.

The inconsistency in censorship rules is likely to lead to a cognitive conflict in the recipients of the text, who are, in this case, adolescents. They might expect rules and systems to which censorship belongs to be rational and consistent since consistent rules create a sense of predictability and control. Therefore, when censorship appears arbitrary, it conflicts with the expected logical governance, thus creating a form of cognitive dissonance (Harmon-Jones, 2019). This dissonance, through which participants experience discomfort as a result of holding contradictory beliefs or behaviours that clash with their expectations (Festinger, 1957), can also manifest as annoyance or dissatisfaction, as it challenges their understanding of how authority should function. As a consequence, the perceived irrationality of censorship amplifies feelings of powerlessness—in other words, not only are they unable to change or influence these rules, but the rules themselves are not consistent or logical.

Additionally, in a context where censorship rules are not applied consistently and clearly, the process of censorship itself can be viewed as unfair by young readers since, according to procedural justice theory, people tend to feel more satisfied with a decision if the process by which it was made is perceived as fair (Thibaut et al., 1975). This perception of unfairness can lead to

frustration and powerlessness because the individuals affected by the practice of censorship might feel like they are being subjected to a system that does not respect principles of fairness or transparency. Finally, it has been argued that people's perceptions of procedural justice can impact their acceptance of decisions and their view of authority (Tyler, 2008), which, in the case of this study, might suggest that the inconsistency observed by the Iranian youth could lead to a decreased trust in and respect for the authorities imposing these rules.

6.7. Final Thoughts and Suggestions

To wrap the interview up, participants were asked two final questions regarding their opinion on what topics should or should not be censored and why, as well as how they think those in charge of the translation and publishing process should handle topics deemed sensitive or controversial. Although some of the interviewees had proactively answered these two in relation to the previously raised questions, the answers will be recorded here separately.

Those who identified as practising Muslims (participants 6, 8, 9, 11, 16) tended to agree that young Muslims should not be exposed to topics against the Islamic Sharia; however, when asked follow-up questions to elaborate on their answers in more detail, they suggested various methods of dealing with the issue. As mentioned in direct quotes in 5.2. and 5.4., one participant (6) believed that morally problematic books should not be translated in the first place, while one participant (11) had a less strict approach and believed certain books that do not abide by Islamic laws in the content should come with a warning.

Two participants (9 and 16) stated that these books should not be available specifically to underage children. It is worth noting that participant 9 stated in the first section of the interview

(5.1.) that they found censorship of subjects such as alcoholic beverages or characters being drunk as ‘weird’ or perhaps as rendering the stories and their characters unusual. In the case of the Muslim participants (6, 8, 9, 11, 16), it is important to consider their beliefs in terms of their own culture and environment, which can help explain the participants’ varied responses to what topics should be censored. For instance, participant 11’s suggestion that books not aligning with Islamic laws should come with a warning rather than being banned outright reflects a more flexible interpretation of cultural norms, which might indicate Post-Conventional Schema in their moral reasoning, where there is a recognition of legal and moral views differing from personal views (Rest et al., 2000).

Moreover, participant 16 had previously answered in section 5.4. that they believe there are more life-threatening laws being practised by the authorities, so censorship is not considered by them to be as significant of an issue in comparison. This signals the fact that the participants’ implicit agreement with censorship in certain cases does not equal their support for or agreement with the current ruling government in Iran. All of these instances further demonstrate that these children each have developed their own nuanced definition of what should or should not be made available to adolescents of their age group and that these definitions vary –even slightly– from one participant to another.

Participants who were not practising Muslims, or were not as strict in their religious practices, i.e., did not adhere to Sharia (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15) also mentioned different subjects in their opinion of what should be allowed in translated children’s literature in Iran; however, in the case of these interviewees, topics mostly revolved around gory subjects and explicit descriptions of violence, or other explicit and perceived age-inappropriate topics, rather than subjects that do not align with Islamic laws. For instance, participant 5 explained: “If a book

contains stuff like rape, or like, describing in detail how someone was tortured or stuff like that, then maybe it shouldn't be easily available." Participant 1 similarly stated: "I don't think a kissing scene is going to damage me mentally, but a murder scene full of blood can have a long-lasting effect on us. So maybe they should come with a trigger warning? I'm not sure."

It appears that for children of this group, topics like drinking, infidelity, displays of affection outside marriage, and other such subjects that are frowned upon in Islam, are not an issue, and they are instead worried about topics of a more violent nature such as rape, torture, or murder. The concerns raised about violent content align with findings by Anderson et al. (2003), suggesting that exposure to violent media can have more direct and lasting effects on young individuals, potentially leading to emotional distress or desensitization to violence. This concern is reflected in participants' suggestions for trigger warnings, indicating an awareness of the potential psychological impacts of such content and a desire for measures that mitigate these effects without resorting to outright censorship.

However, in this group of participants, the criteria were similarly nuanced and varied from one participant to another. In other words, while some believed books containing explicit and violent narratives should not be translated for children at all, another group thought that these books should be available with adequate awareness around them in the form of para-text or trigger warnings. The varied opinions within this group on how to handle sensitive content similarly demonstrate their engagement with the concept of censorship on a complex level. This diversity highlights an individualized approach to what counts as appropriate content, emphasizing their desire for a more transparent censorship process, which they find lacking in the current state of censorship in Iran. To further elaborate, this group also agreed that the current state of censorship, in its ambiguity and oppressiveness, is not the method they would prefer. Their responses suggest

that while these participants reject the traditional cultural norms that dictate censorship based on religious values, they are actively engaging in a discourse about what censorship should instead aim to protect children against. Their perspective seems to be largely informed by a concern for their mental and emotional well-being, advocating for a censorship approach that is more attuned to psychological impacts rather than purely moral or religious considerations.

As for how those in charge of translating and publishing books should approach this issue, one interpretation could be that children appeared to have not given it much thought previous to the study, with some blaming the translator for the omissions. This was mostly the case for those who were involved in fan communities and, therefore, were more passionate about the texts (participants 1, 10, 14). However, it can also be argued that the participants were not given the required knowledge of the publishing process to be able to make an informed judgment. In other words, children's lack of detailed knowledge about translation and consequent publishing processes could be a result of systemic opacity in how information about these processes is disseminated in the first place. This lack of transparency negatively affects children's media literacy, which is essential in their empowerment as critical thinkers, as the absence of media literacy education can lead to misconceptions about how media, including translated texts, is created or manipulated (Hobbs, 2011).

In continuation, it appears that the current educational system in Iran has failed to provide adequate instruction on media production processes and, therefore, has contributed to this lack of awareness. In an environment where understanding media production is a critical component of media literacy that can help individuals discern motivations and biases behind certain texts (Buckingham, 2003), this educational gap in Iranian children's understanding of the mechanics of

book production and translation might prevent them from fully grasping or questioning the roles of translators and publishers in the censorship process.

As a final point, when the processes behind media creation and modification are not transparent, it becomes challenging for young consumers to pinpoint and articulate specific issues related to it. Censorship can be deeply embedded in cultural and media systems, which often results in it being hidden under bureaucratic practices, making it difficult for the audience to identify its mechanisms and impacts (Jansen, 1988). This obfuscation can lead to a misplaced attribution of blame—in this case, towards translators rather than the broader systemic practices of censorship.

6.8. In Comparison with Existing Literature

The findings of this study align with and add to the existing research surrounding censorship in translated children's literature in Iran. Previous studies have highlighted the detrimental effects of restricted access to diverse narratives on children's cognitive and emotional development (Bishop, 2013), which underscores the potential for role confusion and weakened identity formation due to censorship. The interviews corroborate these concerns, as many participants expressed feelings of confusion and frustration when confronted with censored content, confirming the previous assertion that censorship can hinder children's ability to develop a comprehensive sense of self.

Moreover, the findings of these interviews extend the work of Selgi (2016) and Hosseini (2019) by providing concrete examples of specific omissions and their impacts on Iranian children, as well as going further by illustrating the nuanced ways in which these instances of censorship are perceived by the readers themselves, revealing a significant gap between the intended

protective measures of censorship and the actual reception by adolescents. Additionally, the result of these interviews adds a unique perspective by documenting the strategies employed by children to circumvent censorship, such as seeking original texts or using online platforms, and therefore enriching the existing literature by providing a detailed account of how the impacts of censorship manifest in the daily lives of Iranian children and how they actively seek to reclaim their autonomy and access to diverse narratives.

6.9. Concluding Discussion

This chapter attempted to dissect the interplay between censorship, child readers' autonomy, and children's rights through the lens of Iranian youth's experiences with translated children's literature and other areas where censorship takes place. The findings shed light on an environment where censorship not only filters content but is also used by the ruling government to establish and promote certain ideologies. The children's varied responses to these actions highlight a deeper and, at times, conflicting relationship with the government-imposed norms and the inherent desire for authentic, unfiltered knowledge. As a result of this desire, participants engaged with multiple alternative sources of information, including unofficial platforms and foreign texts, which influenced their awareness of censorship and seems to be fostering a critical literacy that extends beyond the immediate context of censorship to a broader critique of socio-political structures of the country.

For many, the act of seeking out uncensored material is not a mere quest for fuller narratives, but a form of intellectual defiance against the state-imposed constraints on children's cognitive and cultural development. This form of resistance is significant in its demonstration of a

shift from passive consumption of media to an active, participatory approach to cultural consumption. In other words, young readers are not just absorbing context but are dynamically involved in constructing their informational landscapes through challenging the narrative that they have been given by the authorities.

Considering this shift, it can be argued that censorship literacy—understanding why and how content is censored—could be as essential as media literacy; therefore, integrating censorship literacy as part of children’s education could help them in critical analysis of the motivations and implications of censorship, fostering a new generation that is both aware of and capable of questioning and challenging the status quo. Such educational initiatives, while not feasible under the regulations of the current regime, could empower adolescents, transforming their marginal role in cultural conversations to active participation in the discourse surrounding censorship, their rights, and freedom of expression.

Chapter 7: Conclusion

This thesis has taken on an in-depth exploration of the phenomenon of censorship in translated children's literature within the Islamic Republic of Iran, focusing on how this practice of censorship takes place and its implications for adolescent readers and their rights. More specifically, this study aimed to answer two research questions: How does censorship via translation take place in children's literature within Iran? Additionally, how is this practice and its impacts on children and their rights perceived by the children themselves? By examining the dynamics of state-imposed censorship, the young minds' perception of it, and its impact on their rights, this research has sought to illuminate the significant and perhaps overlooked impacts of such censorship on Iranian child readers.

The methodological approach adopted for this study was designed to create a deeper understanding of how censorship in Iran is taking place and how it is experienced and perceived by those directly affected by it—in this case, Iranian adolescent readers. To achieve the first objective of the study, three specific translated texts were analyzed, which allowed for a detailed analysis while limiting the breadth of the study. Similarly, for the second part of the study, sixteen interviews were conducted and offered a snapshot rather than a full panorama of the censorship landscape; however, this focused approach proved beneficial in achieving the in-depth understanding required to address the research questions effectively.

The result of the first part of the study, the textual analysis, showed that censorship in Iranian translated children's literature extends beyond the mere exclusion of content that contradicts Islamic values and involves a nuanced process where literature is potentially used as a tool to perpetuate specific ideological narratives favoured by the ruling government. This process

significantly restricts the diversity of literary themes and dilutes the potential for literature to serve as grounds for cultural exchange and intellectual development. In other words, the stringent yet ambiguous controls imposed by the Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance, responsible for meticulous screening of all translated literature, including those of children's, ensure that the content not only avoids conflicting with Islamic principles but also promotes governmental ideologies.

The results of the second part of the study, comprising individual interviews with children, underscore the need for a critical analysis of censorship practices in Iran, particularly those targeting children's literature, which remain ambiguous and understudied as of the time of this research. While seemingly intended to safeguard moral and religious values, these practices seem to inadvertently hinder intellectual freedom, limit young readers' exposure to diverse perspectives, negatively affect adolescents' inclination to read, cause a lack of trust by children toward authorities, result in a kind of learned helplessness due to their rights being irrationally denied, and finally, a cognitive dissonance that could be confusing and uncomfortable for children. Therefore, encouraging a more open literary environment and promoting uncensored access to literature could foster greater intellectual curiosity, cultural understanding, and a sense of security in their fundamental human rights as well as their reading habits. As a result, future policies should more closely consider the balance between ideological preservation and the promotion of intellectual freedom, ensuring that literature can fulfil its potential as a tool for cultural enrichment and personal development.

This study raises a number of significant questions that warrant further investigation. One key area for future research is the impact of censorship on children's development of critical thinking skills. Understanding whether and how censorship might stifle or even promote critical

engagement with texts could provide important insights into the broader educational and social implications of such practices and policies. In addition, comparative studies involving other contexts, such as countries with similar political or cultural environments, could illuminate how different censorship mechanisms affect literary development and cultural exchange. Expanding the scope to include digital literature and online reading platforms could also offer valuable perspectives on how the rise of technology is changing the dynamics of censorship and free access to information.

Finally, this thesis makes several contributions to the field of censorship studies and children's literature by highlighting the complex process from translation to publication during which censorship takes place, adding depth to our understanding of the translation process as a site of cultural negotiation and control. Furthermore, by focusing on Iran as the context of the study, where political and religious ideologies heavily impact literary production and availability and where previously there has not been much research on this issue despite its prevalence, this study enriches both the local and the global discourse on how censorship can shape the intellectual landscape of a society, especially for children at a stage in their lives where they are developing their autonomous identities.

As Iran continues to navigate the uneven terrain of modernity and tradition, in addition to the contrast between people's growing secularity and the country's Islamic constitution, the insights provided by this research could signal the need for more nuanced and effective approaches to protecting children from potentially harmful material, which may be achieved by a democratic government in Iran in the future.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

سوالات مصاحبه

1. آیا می‌توانید تجربه‌ی کلی خود از خواندن کتاب‌های هری پاتر و سنگ جادو، ماجراهای شرلوک هولمز، و کد داوینچی را توصیف کنید؟
2. آیا به نظرتان محتوای این کتاب‌ها ناقص یا ویرایش‌شده بودند؟ اگر بله، می‌توانید چند مثال بزنید؟
3. هنگام خواندن هری پاتر و سنگ جادو، آیا متوجه می‌شدید که چیزی که انتظار می‌رفت ممکن است حذف یا تغییر یافته باشد، مانند مثل اشاره به موارد خاص فرهنگی؟
4. در ماجراهای شرلوک هولمز، آیا داستان‌ها یا شخصیت‌هایی بودند که شما آن‌ها را می‌شناختید اما در نسخه‌ای که خواندید حضور نداشتند؟
5. کد داوینچی به عنوان یک کتاب بحث‌برانگیز شناخته می‌شود و به صورت رسمی در داخل کشور چاپ نمی‌شود. به نظر شما کدام بخش‌های کتاب باعث ممنوعیت آن شده‌اند؟
6. از اصطلاح "سانسور" چه درکی دارید؟ می‌توانید مثال‌هایی از نحوه مواجهه با آن در مواد خواندنی خود بیاورید؟
7. چه احساسی نسبت به این دارید که برخی از محتواهای کتاب‌هایی که خوانده‌اید ممکن است سانسور یا حذف شده باشند؟
8. به نظرتان سانسور به چه شکلی بر حقوق شما به عنوان یک نوجوان و یک خواننده‌ی کتاب تأثیر می‌گذارد؟
9. وقتی متوجه می‌شوید که ممکن است حذفیات یا ویرایش‌هایی در این کتاب‌ها وجود داشته باشد، به عنوان یک خواننده چه احساسی پیدا می‌کنید؟
10. بر اساس تجربه و دانشتان، سانسور در ادبیات ایران چقدر رایج است؟
11. نظرتان درباره تأثیر سانسور بر توانایی کودکان در دسترسی به متون و ایده‌های متنوع چیست؟
12. اگر شما می‌توانستید تصمیم بگیرید، چگونه دوست داشتید کتاب‌ها برای خوانندگان هم‌سن شما انتخاب یا اصلاح شوند؟

13. آیا فکر می‌کنید موضوعات یا نوع کتاب‌هایی وجود دارند که نباید برای خوانندگان جوان سانسور شوند؟ چرا یا

چرا نه؟

14. به نظرتان نویسندگان و ناشران چگونه باید با موضوعاتی که ممکن است حساس یا بحث‌برانگیز باشند برخورد

کنند؟

Interview Questions (translated to English)

1. Can you describe your overall experience reading *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone*, *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, and *The Da Vinci Code*?
2. Did anything about the content of these books seem incomplete or edited to you? If yes, could you give some examples?
3. While reading *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone*, did you notice any moments where something expected might have been missing or altered, such as references to behaviors or cultural elements?
4. In *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, were there any stories or characters you knew of but found missing in the version you read?
5. *The Da Vinci Code* is known to be controversial; and it's not officially available inside the country in print. What parts of the book do you think caused the banning?
6. What do you understand by the term "censorship"? Can you give examples of how you have encountered it in your reading materials?
7. How do you feel about the fact that some content in the books you read might have been censored or removed?
8. In what ways do you think censorship affects your rights as a young person and young reader?

9. How did realizing there might be omissions or edits in these books make you feel as a reader?
10. How common do you think censorship is in literature in Iran, based on your experience and knowledge?
11. What are your thoughts on the impact of censorship on children's ability to access a wide range of texts and ideas?
12. If you could decide, how would you like to see books selected or modified for readers in your age group?
13. Do you think there are topics or types of books that should not be censored for young readers? Why or why not?
14. How do you think authors and publishers should handle topics that might be considered sensitive or controversial?

Appendix 2

فرم رضایت‌نامه‌ی آگاهانه برای نوجوانان شرکت‌کننده در مصاحبه

عنوان مطالعه: سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران

محقق اصلی و مصاحبه‌کننده: مریم انصاری

موسسه آموزشی: دانشگاه تیلبورگ

شماره تماس: (حذف شده)

آدرس ایمیل: (حذف شده)

مقدمه: شما به شرکت در یک مطالعه تحقیقاتی درباره سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران دعوت شده‌اید. قبل از تصمیم‌گیری برای شرکت در این تحقیق، مهم است که بدانید چرا این تحقیق انجام می‌شود و چه مواردی در آن دخیل است. لطفاً اطلاعات زیر را با دقت بخوانید و هر سؤالی دارید، بپرسید.

هدف مطالعه: هدف این مطالعه بررسی چگونگی اعمال سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران و تأثیرات آن بر درک حقوق و تجربیات خواندن کودکان است.

روش‌ها: اگر موافقت کنید که در این مطالعه شرکت کنید، از شما خواسته می‌شود که:

1. ترجمه‌های فارسی سه کتاب: "هری پاتر و سنگ جادو"، "ماجراهای شرلوک هولمز" و "کد داوینچی" را بخوانید.

2. در یک مصاحبه فردی از طریق گوگل میتس شرکت کنید که حدود 45 تا 60 دقیقه طول می‌کشد و در آن درباره

تجربه خواندن و نظرات شما درباره سانسور پرسیده می‌شود.

شرکت داوطلبانه: شرکت شما در این مطالعه کاملاً داوطلبانه است. شما می‌توانید در هر زمانی بدون ارائه دلیل و بدون هیچ پیامد منفی‌ای از شرکت در این مطالعه انصراف دهید.

محرمانگی: تمام اطلاعاتی که ارائه می‌دهید محرمانه خواهد بود. پاسخ‌های شما ناشناس خواهد بود و هیچ اطلاعات شناسایی‌شده‌ای در گزارش‌ها یا انتشارات ناشی از این مطالعه به اشتراک گذاشته نخواهد شد.

مزایا و مخاطرات: هیچ مزیت مستقیمی برای شما در شرکت در این مطالعه وجود ندارد. با این حال، پاسخ‌های شما ممکن است به ما کمک کند تا تأثیر سانسور بر خوانندگان جوان در ایران را درک کنیم. هیچ خطر قابل پیش‌بینی‌ای در ارتباط با شرکت در این مطالعه وجود ندارد.

رضایت: من اطلاعات بالا را خوانده‌ام و فرصت پرسیدن سوالات را داشته‌ام. من می‌دانم که شرکت من داوطلبانه است و می‌توانم در هر زمانی انصراف دهم. با امضای زیر، من رضایت خود را برای شرکت در این مطالعه اعلام می‌کنم.

تاریخ:

امضاء:

نام:

Informed Consent Form for Interview Participants (English translation)

Title of the Study: Censorship in Translated Children's Literature in Iran

Principal Researcher and Interviewer: Maryam Ansari

Institution: Tilburg University

Phone Number: [redacted]

Email Address: [redacted]

Introduction: You are being invited to take part in a research study about censorship in translated children's literature in Iran. Before you decide to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and ask any questions you may have.

Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this study is to investigate how censorship in translated children's literature is implemented in Iran and how it affects children's perception of their rights and reading experiences.

Procedures: If you agree to participate, you will be asked to:

1. Read the Persian translations of three books: *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone*, *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, and *The Da Vinci Code*.
2. Participate in an individual interview via Google Meets, lasting between 45 to 60 minutes, where you will be asked about your reading experience and thoughts on censorship.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You can choose not to participate or withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without any negative consequences.

Confidentiality: All information you provide will be kept confidential. Your responses will be anonymized, and no identifying information will be shared in any reports or publications resulting from this study.

Benefits and Risks: There are no direct benefits to you for participating in this study. However, your responses may help us understand the impact of censorship on young readers in Iran. There are no foreseeable risks associated with participation in this study.

Consent: I have read the information provided above and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time. By signing below, I consent to participate in this study.

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Appendix 3

فرم رضایت‌نامه‌ی آگاهانه برای والدین یا قیم قانونی

عنوان مطالعه: سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران

محقق اصلی و مصاحبه‌کننده: مریم انصاری

موسسه آموزشی: دانشگاه تیلبورگ

شماره تماس: (حذف شده)

آدرس ایمیل: (حذف شده)

مقدمه: فرزند شما به شرکت در یک مطالعه تحقیقاتی درباره سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران دعوت شده‌است. قبل از تصمیم‌گیری برای اجازه دادن به فرزندتان برای شرکت در این تحقیق، مهم است که بدانید چرا این تحقیق انجام می‌شود و چه مواردی در آن دخیل است. لطفاً اطلاعات زیر را با دقت بخوانید و هر سؤالی دارید، بپرسید.

هدف مطالعه: هدف این مطالعه بررسی چگونگی اعمال سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران و تأثیرات آن بر درک حقوق و تجربیات خواندن کودکان است.

روش‌ها: اگر موافقت کنید که فرزندتان در این مطالعه شرکت کند، از او خواسته می‌شود که:

1. ترجمه‌های فارسی سه کتاب: "هری پاتر و سنگ جادو"، "ماجراهای شرلوک هولمز" و "کد داوینچی" را بخواند.
2. در یک مصاحبه فردی از طریق گوگل میتس شرکت کند که حدود 45 تا 60 دقیقه طول می‌کشد و در آن درباره تجربه خواندن و نظرات او درباره سانسور پرسیده می‌شود.

شرکت داوطلبانه: شرکت فرزندتان در این مطالعه کاملاً داوطلبانه است. او می‌تواند در هر زمانی بدون ارائه دلیل و بدون هیچ پیامد منفی‌ای از شرکت در این مطالعه انصراف دهد.

محرمانگی: تمام اطلاعات ارائه شده توسط فرزند شما محرمانه خواهد بود. پاسخ‌های او ناشناس خواهد بود و هیچ اطلاعات شناسایی‌شده‌ای در گزارش‌ها یا انتشارات ناشی از این مطالعه به اشتراک گذاشته نخواهد شد.

مزایا و مخاطرات: هیچ مزیت مستقیمی برای فرزند شما در شرکت در این مطالعه وجود ندارد. با این حال، پاسخ‌های او ممکن است به ما کمک کند تا تأثیر سانسور بر خوانندگان جوان در ایران را درک کنیم. هیچ خطر قابل پیش‌بینی‌ای در ارتباط با شرکت در این مطالعه وجود ندارد.

رضایت: من اطلاعات بالا را خوانده‌ام و فرصت پرسیدن سوالات را داشته‌ام. من می‌دانم که شرکت فرزندم داوطلبانه است و او می‌تواند در هر زمانی انصراف دهد. با امضای زیر، من رضایت خود را برای شرکت فرزندم در این مطالعه اعلام می‌کنم.

نام فرزند: _____ نام والد/قیم: _____ امضاء والد/قیم: _____ تاریخ: _____

Informed Consent Form for Legal Guardians (English translation)

Title of the Study: Censorship in Translated Children's Literature in Iran

Principal Researcher and Interviewer: Maryam Ansari

Institution: Tilburg University

Phone Number: [redacted]

Email Address: [redacted]

Introduction: Your child is being invited to participate in a research study about censorship in translated children’s literature in Iran. Before you decide to allow your child to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and ask any questions you may have.

Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this study is to investigate how censorship in translated children’s literature is implemented in Iran and how it affects children’s perception of their rights and reading experiences.

Procedures: If you consent to your child’s participation, they will be asked to:

1. Read the Persian translations of three books: *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer’s Stone*, *The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes*, and *The Da Vinci Code*.
2. Participate in an individual interview via Google Meets, lasting between 45 to 60 minutes, where they will be asked about their reading experience and thoughts on censorship.

Voluntary Participation: Your child’s participation in this study is entirely voluntary. They can choose not to participate or withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without any negative consequences.

Confidentiality: All information provided by your child will be kept confidential. Their responses will be anonymized, and no identifying information will be shared in any reports or publications resulting from this study.

Benefits and Risks: There are no direct benefits to your child for participating in this study. However, their responses may help us understand the impact of censorship on young readers in Iran. There are no foreseeable risks associated with participation in this study.

Consent: I have read the information provided above and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my child's participation is voluntary and that they can withdraw at any time. By signing below, I consent to my child's participation in this study.

Child's Name:

Parent/Guardian Name:

Parent/Guardian Signature:

Date:

Appendix 4

فرم رضایت‌نامه‌ی آگاهانه برای شخص سوم حاضر در مصاحبه

عنوان مطالعه: سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران

محقق اصلی و مصاحبه‌کننده: مریم انصاری

موسسه آموزشی: دانشگاه تیلبورگ

شماره تماس: (حذف شده)

آدرس ایمیل: (حذف شده)

مقدمه: شما به حضور در یک مصاحبه به عنوان بخشی از یک مطالعه تحقیقاتی درباره سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران دعوت شده‌اید. قبل از تصمیم‌گیری برای شرکت، مهم است که بدانید چرا این تحقیق انجام می‌شود و چه مواردی در آن دخیل است. لطفاً اطلاعات زیر را با دقت بخوانید و هر سؤالی دارید، بپرسید.

هدف مطالعه: هدف این مطالعه بررسی چگونگی اعمال سانسور در ادبیات کودک و نوجوان ترجمه‌شده در ایران و تأثیرات آن بر درک حقوق و تجربیات خواندن کودکان است.

روش‌ها: اگر موافقت کنید که در مصاحبه حضور داشته باشید، از شما خواسته می‌شود که:

1. در مصاحبه فردی از طریق گوگل میتس که حدود 45 تا 60 دقیقه طول می‌کشد، حضور داشته باشید.

شرکت داوطلبانه: شرکت شما در این مطالعه کاملاً داوطلبانه است. شما می‌توانید در هر زمانی بدون ارائه دلیل و بدون هیچ پیامد منفی‌ای از شرکت در این مطالعه انصراف دهید.

محرمانگی: تمام اطلاعات ارائه شده در طول مصاحبه محرمانه خواهد بود. پاسخها ناشناس خواهد بود و هیچ اطلاعات شناسایی شده‌ای در گزارش‌ها یا انتشارات ناشی از این مطالعه به اشتراک گذاشته نخواهد شد.

مزایا و مخاطرات: هیچ مزیت مستقیمی برای شما در شرکت در این مطالعه وجود ندارد. با این حال، حضور شما ممکن است به اطمینان خاطر و امنیت شرکت‌کننده کمک کند. هیچ خطر قابل پیش‌بینی‌ای در ارتباط با شرکت در این مطالعه وجود ندارد.

رضایت: من اطلاعات بالا را خوانده‌ام و فرصت پرسیدن سوالات را داشته‌ام. من می‌دانم که شرکت من داوطلبانه است و می‌توانم در هر زمانی انصراف دهم. با امضای زیر، من رضایت خود را برای حضور در مصاحبه این مطالعه اعلام می‌کنم.

تاریخ:

امضاء:

نام:

Informed Consent Form for Third Person Present During Interview (English translation)

Title of the Study: Censorship in Translated Children's Literature in Iran

Principal Researcher and Interviewer: Maryam Ansari

Institution: Tilburg University

Phone Number: [redacted]

Email Address: [redacted]

Introduction: You are being invited to be present during an interview as part of a research study about censorship in translated children’s literature in Iran. Before you decide to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and ask any questions you may have.

Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this study is to investigate how censorship in translated children’s literature is implemented in Iran and how it affects children’s perception of their rights and reading experiences.

Procedures: If you agree to be present during the interview, you will be asked to:

1. Sit in during the individual interview of the participant via Google Meets, lasting between 45 to 60 minutes.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You can choose not to participate or withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without any negative consequences.

Confidentiality: All information provided during the interview will be kept confidential. Responses will be anonymized, and no identifying information will be shared in any reports or publications resulting from this study.

Benefits and Risks: There are no direct benefits to you for participating in this study. However, your presence may help ensure the comfort and safety of the participant. There are no foreseeable risks associated with participation in this study.

Consent: I have read the information provided above and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time. By signing below, I consent to be present during the interview for this study.

Name:

Signature:

Date: